

5.2 Deliverable

Growing Map of City Production Capacity and Material Flows

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Abstract (for public dissemination only)	The Growing Map of City Production Capacity and Material Flows presents first a pilot-specific data collection support and the mapping of the Material Journeys Within a City for the 6 city pilots of the REFLOW project: Paris, Berlin, Amsterdam, Vejle, Cluj-Napoca, Milan. This document also details the methodology for starting a primary data collection at a City level, as well as the methodology for the mapping building. Efforts have been put into the replicability, the adaptability, and the user-friendliness of the results. To ensure the sustainability of the results, they will be implemented in the REFLOW open-source dashboard: the Open Data Dashboard, and the data will feed the REFLOW OS. To enhance Pilot's cooperation and works' interdependencies, data collection is being implemented in the Pilot Cities Framework. General Data Protection Regulation is ensured.

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Revision History

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D5.2: Growing Map of City Production Capacity and Material Flows [18]

will provides a wide and comprehensive scenario of the six cities' material flows (Amsterdam, Paris, Berlin, Milan, Vejle, and Cluj-Napoca) through collection and analysis of data on materials, making use of open data/patterns, and virtualization of flows within the urban and peri-urban ecosystems.

Executive summary

Establishing a city-wide Circular Economy requires the mapping of the material flow within the city and its production capacity. It allows stakeholders to have a clear visibility of the city production capacity, while the material focus clears the available information to identify key areas of improvement and/or business opportunities.

The present document provides a wide and comprehensive scenario of the six REFLOW pilot cities material flows (Amsterdam, Paris, Berlin, Milan, Vejle and Cluj-Napoca). It focuses on developing for each pilots' material (wood, plastic, textile, wastewater heat, urban energy and food waste) a **first level understanding** of the **material journeys through the key material transformations processes**, undergone during its life cycle.

The Growing map of City Production Capacity and Material Flows results are two-fold. Firstly, a **standardized data collection methodology** and template, focused on identifying materials flows and related actors' interactions within the city, were created. Secondly, developing a **comprehensive overview** of the material transformation journey, through a visual **mapping**, the mapping of the Material Journeys Within a City, of the different processes and material states. Those mappings are developed through collection and analysis of data on materials, making use of open data and virtualization of flows within the urban and peri-urban ecosystems. Data presented in each pilot cities mapping come from both desk research on material transformation processes for each city, as well as interviews of the pilot's members.

Those solutions are designed to answer REFLOW pilot city current needs, as well as to be a **turnkey solution**, with a strong focus on **replicability** for results' production. The methodology used to develop the solutions are documented throughout the report to support future cities taking a similar route. Technical documentation is available in the annex. In addition, the solutions are **standardized** to be easily adapted to new context and new material with minimal adaptation work required. Results are **user-friendly** and require little formation to be used. Data collection and mapping of the Material Journeys Within a City lean on REFLOW tools to operate: Open Data Dashboard, the REFLOW SharePoint and the Pilot Cities Framework.

The **methodology for primary data collection** based on interviews, is accessible both as an excel template spreadsheet, shared on the General Data Protection Regulation-compliant (GDPR) REFLOW SharePoint, and on the REFLOW "Pilot Cities Framework". The "Pilot Cities Framework" is a digital platform, defined as a "system for guiding and aligning, fostering iterative project development, monitoring the progress and boosting knowledge exchange between the cities and partners" (D5.1 Pilot Coordination, Framework and Planning) The mapping of the Material Journeys within a City, the **visual diagram showing the material journey** specific for each pilot, is planned to be implemented on the Open Data Dashboard. Due to development schedule, the implementation on the Open Data Dashboard will be finalized after the submission of this deliverable.

However, both the data collected in the Pilot Cities Framework, and the data and mappings will directly feed in the Open Data Dashboard once it is launched. A visualisation module of the material flow will be included in the dashboard. Open Data Dashboard developed within the

REFLOW project is meant to be the visually appealing interface between the open data and the end-user. It allows pilot cities to implement their data as well as to use publicly available open data, to create their own dashboards to display their data. The city's pilots can then compose their dashboards using a specific selection of modules (charts, diagrams ...) to display their data.

The REFLOW Pilot Cities Framework is an internal tool developed by the WAAG that aligns and monitors the cities by mapping in a system the same structure and the same typology of information across topics. The data collected by the pilot cities using the methodology developed will be stored in the Pilot Cities Framework.

The mapping of the Material Journey's Within a City's presented in this document have been developed using Power BI tools, to produce user friendly visuals, while the final visualization tool is being developed.

Results presented in this deliverable clarify the material processes and transformations within each city's pilots, while providing a wide and comprehensive scenario of the six cities' material flows.

From the ecosystem's point of view, both primary data collection and the **mapping of the Wood's Journeys Within Paris**, have highlighted the value material's data have. Storage and control over the shape and dimensions of the wood have been found to be the most critical issues while collecting data among the ecosystems.

Berlin Pilot has a simple material flow to sketch-up: wastewater is feeding the sewer system. However, the "**mapping of the Wastewater heat journeys within Berlin**" has shown the flexibility of the heat recovering system within the sewage system chain.

While presenting "**the mapping of the Home Textile's Journeys Within Amsterdam**", some rare path occurrences or processes and transformations still in development have been uncovered, stimulating potential business opportunities.

The **mapping of Plastics' journeys Within Vejle** gives a wide and comprehensive overview of the different path the plastic can take once correctly sorted. The mapping highlighted the disparities of treatment between the plastic's families. It showed also how laws can impact the mapping of Material Journeys Within a City, regarding specific treatment of PVC.

While many sources of urban energy have been identified nationally in Romania, the legislation restrict the access to local information about energy. The pilot city has access to national percentage of energy sources, but no details regarding their city precisely, as the national electrical network collecting energy from all sources. The impact on the non-accessibility of local data is emphasized in the **mapping of Plastics' journeys Within Cluj-Napoca**.

Primary Data collection formalization brought by the methodology helped organizing and conducting data collection for the Milan Pilot. In addition to "**the mapping of the food leftovers' Journeys Within Milan**" helped the Pilot to clarify and sketch up the different processes and transformation the pilot might focus on to retrieve data.

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1. Introduction

REFLOW is an EU H2020 funded project, from 2019 to 2022, that seeks to understand and transform urban material flows and to co-create and test circular and regenerative solutions at business, governance, and citizen levels. It has received funding from the European Union Innovation and Research Program, under the Grant Agreement No. 820937.

The vision of REFLOW is to develop transition paths towards circular and regenerative cities by re-localising production and re-configuring material flows. REFLOW uses Fab Labs and Makerspaces as catalysers of systemic change in urban and peri-urban environments. It does so through the implementation of Circular Economy (CE) projects in six Pilots throughout Europe. These Pilots aim to reduce material consumption, maximize multifunctional use of (public) spaces and develop regenerative practices, contributing to the overall project goal to enable, visualize and regulate free movement of resources, people, (technological) knowledge, and commons.

1.1 Objectives of the Deliverable

1.1.1 Objectives and Sub-sets

This present deliverable aims to provide a wide and comprehensive scenario of the six cities' **material flows** (Amsterdam, Paris, Berlin, Milan, Vejle, and Cluj-Napoca) through collection and analysis of data on materials, making use of open data/patterns, and **virtualization of flows** within the urban and peri-urban ecosystems.

This deliverable will allow to have a **clear understanding of each material flow** both in terms of the steps happening in the lifecycle of the material and in terms of opportunities that circular practices can offer to the city.

Mapping focuses on the different states of the material during its life. Understanding what the various stages of the life cycle are, and what it means in terms of technical properties of the material, are crucial to develop tailored circular solutions.

This mapping end uses are multiple: from helping the REFLOW pilot's team to have a clear and define understanding of the flow of material tracked by each city, to create communication support to foster citizens and municipality involvement through education. It also allows to the different stakeholders to have a better visibility on the circular economy processes they could get involved in, and the impact of taking steps into circular process.

The **main objective** of the deliverable is to build a comprehensive overview of the six REFLOW cities' material life cycle's transformation points to:

- **raise awareness** about the life cycle of cities.
- clearly **identify the inputs** of new resources, transformations, and outputs, to highlight:
 - the points that could potentially offer business opportunities
 - the positive impacts offered by a circular economy
- the importance of the circularity transition

The results (mapping and databases) have to be easily accessible, and as user-friendly and inclusive as possible.

1.1.2 Milestones and targets

In order to reach this goal, a subset of goals has been defined as follow:

- Scheming comprehensive life cycles and their stakes to spread awareness among the widest population
- Understanding the dynamic of the material life cycle within the city.
- Identifying the different steps between linear and circular paths of the six city's pilots' materials life cycles

Three targets have been identified: the public in general, the actors of the circularity (designers, public actors, makers), and the REFLOW partners.

Towards the actors of the circularity, the stakes are making visible the fluxes and clear enough to highlight businesses opportunities. Towards the REFLOW partners (consortium members), the stakes are building a first level of understanding for other work packages, enhancing the understanding of the material journey, and organizing data.

1.2 Vision, starting situation and approach

1.2.1 Vision and replicability

The wide and comprehensive mapping as well as the primary data collection have been set to be **easily replicable and adaptable** to each city's needs, as the chapter 2 will further present.

The mapping must be developed on a similar structure for each pilot and co-created with all the pilots to foster for their diverse needs. Hence, a dashboard has been created (chapter 2), based on a common basis (same information requirements and layout for homogeneity and standardized contents) for the pilots, so that the mapping of the Material Journeys Within a City would be developed from a similar data structure. Along with this map, a method for data collection has been built in the form of an interview protocol and interview material circularity transition a city might take on the Pilot Cities Framework, an internal tool developed by the WAAG to align and monitor the cities by mapping in a system the same structure and the same typology of information across topics (D5.1 Pilot Coordination, Framework and Planning).

The **Pilot Cities Framework** is a digital platform, defined as "system for guiding and aligning, fostering iterative project development, monitoring the progress and boosting knowledge exchange between the cities and partners, over the lifespan of the project and possibly beyond." Moreover, The **Pilot Cities Framework** has been created to facilitate the interdependencies between Pilot Cities and also between REFLOW works (D5.1 Pilot Coordination, Framework and Planning).

In line with the project and pilot's vision, the mapping of the Material Journeys Within a City and the data collection methodology have been developed as accessible, intuitive and replicable, and a methodology guide is being created so that this process will be a turnkey solution and easy to replicate.

1.2.2 Starting situation

Workshops have been organized with the city's pilots as a start of an iterative process, to ensure a good communication and that the mapping of the Material Journeys Within a City was consistent with each city's scenarios. This iterative process consisted in workshops organized with each city's pilot as well as cooperation on documentation's sharing and writing about materials' journeys within each pilots' scenario.

From the first workshop, key users and the stakes for each city were highlighted.

Key users by pilot:

- Paris: Event partners / SME for material transformation
- Amsterdam: Citizens, designers, teachers, municipality
- Cluj-Napoca: citizens, municipality, municipality agents
- Milan: stall owners, AMSA, SO.GE.MI, food policy, others municipality's department (commerce)
- Vejle: stakeholders, Municipality, citizens
- Berlin: potential stakeholders, students

Two typologies of users and main use cases have been identified:

- Citizens and municipality: For those users, the main purpose of the mapping of the Material Journeys Within a City are sensitization, knowledge sharing and communication. The mapping of the Material Journeys Within a City created should be used as a clear and concise communication means to bring clarity on the material transformation journey.
- Professional involved in the flow of material (stakeholders): For those users, the main purpose of the deliverable are visualisation of the different material flow and actors involved, understanding of the material flow journey as a basis for deeper analysis and visibility on critical steps to help decision making on how to increase circularity and where to focus efforts.

During the workshop, the following features were identified as important for the different pilots.

- Visually representing the different steps of the material life path and its evolution (Lifepath of the material / material state change / energy flow)
- Being able to export the database used in the mapping (material list)
- Geographically representing the flow of material
 - o What happens in that process?
 - o percentage of renewed energy production and origin
 - o Number of potential interaction opportunities among actors
- Material description
 - o (kg, meters, pattern, colors, composition...)
 - o Footprint of the flow
- Educational content
 - o tips and tricks on how to consume less
 - o circular key commons values to be shared amongst stakeholders
- Timeline/ evolution
 - o Being able to see N / N+1 result for a similar event / resource hub
 - o See the evolution of energy consumption

Overall, the amount and granularity of data available in each pilot city is heterogenous. Some city's pilots already have data collected, especially Berlin (waste heat) and Cluj-Napoca (urban energy). Both pilots are managing resources which measurements are already standardized (urban energy and waste heat) and usually handled by technical profile on pre-defined data bases. For the others, the levels of information available with the different stakeholders aren't consistent in the level of details.

Some information highlighted in the features list above will be later included in future REFLOW deliverable and thus will not be included in this work: exhaustive list of volumes/weight/pieces of material handled by each city (Urban Metabolism Strategy Report). However, to facilitate this work and initiate the data collection awareness among stakeholders, a primary data collection of material is included in this deliverable.

The geographical data of the material flows are collected but are not represented on the mapping of the Material Journeys Within a City, considering the heterogeneous nature of the availability of this information. This heterogenous and incomplete nature of the data would have led in a biased analysis and to false conclusion. However, the data collected with the deliverable methodology will allow geographical representation of flows once the next deliverable City Ecosystem Design for each pilot city will be clearly defined.

Primary data is defined here as information about all the categories defined above, collected from stakeholders of each city's pilots' scenario. This primary data -when data are not already available in a standardized shape- is meant to raise awareness among the pilot's scenario's network about the value of these information's, the importance of structuring them. It is also a mean to bring stakeholders to set up methods to be able to measure their relevant data, to facilitate the future work (D3.3 Urban Metabolism Strategy Report due in M36).

1.2.3 Approach

An ideation workshop has been organized with all pilots' teams to engage them with the Mapping of City Production Capacity and Material Flows task and ensure that all pilot cities are involved in the requirements definitions. The workshop was used to define key users, key features and visuals, start the process of defining a common structure of information and align on the vision. The first milestone of setting up a wide and comprehensive mapping of the pilot's cities materials, mapping of the Material Journeys Within a City, create a common vision for the end goal, brainstorm on features and visualisation ideas, and work.

The workshop was defined going back and forth with both Metabolic and the WAAG teams for feedback and improvements.

The focus points were:

- Getting a **clear vision of the key objectives** of the mapping of the Material Journeys Within a City and how it is interconnected with other tasks.
- Define the **roadmap of the workshop**: objectives and action plan. What is the duration of each exercise? When and how do we do the workshop?
- **Align on the task** presentation to ensure that there is no confusion on the vision and objectives of the task.

After the workshop, we summarized the main objectives, relevant information given through the session by the pilots, key ideas on both features and visualisation, and we defined a requirements specification guide to drive us through the task completion. This requirements specification guide has then been reviewed throughout the definition of the task.

Taking the findings of the workshop into account, the mapping of the Material Journeys Within a City was defined for each pilot city as well as a data collection methodology. These results were presented and completed by each pilot through pilot cities specific workshops to fit their needs as closely as possible, as detailed previously in this report. Feedbacks on both the mapping and the template were integrated into the final mapping of the Material Journeys Within a City.

Table 1 Timeline of deliverable design through workshop in 2020

Mid-June	Pre workshop session: key actor chain
Start of July	1 st online workshop Defining key users Key features Common template
July – august – September	Data collection methodology definition Material journey mapping development
October	Workshop 2: feedback on the template and mapping and improvements Implementation of the template on the Pilot Cities Framework

1.3 Structure of the deliverable 5.2

This deliverable will present step by step the methodology used for building the Growing Map of City Production Capacity and Material Flows in chapter 2. Methodology for the primary data collection and the definition of the data collection template are described. The methodology for implementing the mapping of the Material Flows Within a City is also explained.

In chapter 3, the data collection methodology is then applied to the 6 REFLOW Pilot cities, presenting each city specific templates. The Mapping of the Materials Flows within a City are presented for each REFLOW pilot city, alongside with a description of the material flows journeys defined through desk research and interviews with the pilots. Use cases and possible improvements of each pilot city mappings are presented.

Finally, the different outcomes are summed-up, and the next steps are described in chapter 4.

2. Methodology for a Growing Map of City Production Capacity and Material Flows

The different outputs of the workshop helped in drawing a better understanding of the different pilot's expectations from the Mapping of City Production Capacity and Material Flows task. From the different workshop's findings, the pilot's expectations for the data visualisation and the layout of the map were generalized.

The Paris pilot team, Metabolic and WAAG REFLOW partners worked together to ensure that the scope of the data collection methodology developed in Mapping of City Production Capacity and Material Flows task was complementary, and not overlapping, with the work done by Metabolic on material flow analysis for each pilot city scenarios.

The first definition and description of the task Mapping of City Production Capacity and Material Flows had been collectively found to be too material flow-centered and helped us define that the main interest for this task was the material states and transformations.

This led to a redesign of the task, focusing on material transformation and journey, rather than on volumes and localisation for the mapping. In that way, the methodology and mapping developed can be used as a starting point for the material flow analysis process, without there being confusion on the role of each analysis.

The data collected through the Mapping of City Production Capacity and Material Flows task give a first scheme of what would be included in an MFA, but with much less details. It can be used for cities that do not have any data, or clear understanding of the material flow of their cities to get a first level understanding of their local situation. However, it is not equivalent as less precise, and does not include the analysis of the results to give insights. It can serve as a basis for further detailed data collection in the MFA process. It gives an overview of the process.

Although the wide public and the circular actors' interests had been identified at an early stage, the redesigning process identified the task " Mapping of City Production Capacity and Material Flows" as a valuable input for many other work packages, as a first level understanding work.

From this redesign process, the Growing map of city production capacity and material flows deliverable was defined as two parts:

- A data collection methodology and template to collect primary information
- A mapping of the Material Journeys Within a City

2.1 Primary Data Collection

Primary data as defined in the chapter 1, includes: **steps of the material life cycle** and its evolution (Lifepath of the material / material state change / energy flow), **geolocation of the material**, information about the **nature and the state of the material** (material description), **N / N+1 result for a similar event / resource hub**.

Primary data -when data are not already available in a standardized shape- are not collected in an exhaustive way for stakeholder's city's pilots as some stakeholders do have access to them and some do not. However, they are meant to constitute a solid base on which to rely for the "City Ecosystem Design for each pilot city", led by Metabolic. It is also a mean to bring stakeholders to set up methods to be able to measure their relevant data, to facilitate the future work (Urban Metabolism Strategy Report).

As such, the Primary data Collection comes with a Primary Data collection methodology for replicability purposes. The goals here are to ensure first, to a certain extent, consistency in data collection, and second that any city wanting to begin its circular transition can start using this methodology to build its database.

The first part of the deliverable "Growing Map of City Production Capacity and Material Flows" is the development of a data collection methodology through interview-based templates. This methodology is twofold: firstly, it is designed for **each REFLOW pilot material stream**, to be used as a basis for data collection regarding material flow and key actors. Secondly, it is designed to be **used by future cities** starting their transition to circularity.

The data collection template and methodology have been designed with the following criteria in mind.

Criteria for the data collection methodology:

- The data collection must intervene as a **primary step**, for a city that wishes to **begin its circular transition** and wishes to collect data and has no data available to measure its environmental or social performance. In this context, the probability that the ecosystem is not aware of the importance of collecting the specific data that must be gathered for an in-depth flow analysis, is high.
- When collecting data for a new process, on a voluntary basis, one must consider some practical aspects: as the partners might not have all the specific data available, the data collection must be:
 - **Flexible**
 - **not time consuming**
 - **easily understandable.**
- First, as one of the requirements of the REFLOW results in general, the methodology shall be **replicable** to another city. The general form of the collection data and the methodology behind it must be the same for each pilot.
- However, its content shall be adapted to each material, and thus the content must be pilot-specific.

Criteria for the data collection template:

With those objectives, a template was built for data collection.

- As a result of the lack of available standardized data at the beginning of a circular transition, one of the main requirements of this template was to provide **flexibility** in the collection of information.
- From this starting point the template has been thought as an **interview** to allow flexibility. There is no minimum data required to be filled in, but **each information filled can directly feed the mapping**. With that objective, the data collection template has been constructed in a **general form but with a pilot specific content**, to facilitate the **replicability**.

By starting the process of data collection, cities will raise questions among the ecosystem, and stimulate the willingness of partners to collect of partners to collect more precise data for their own communication purposes or for their process improvements and business growth.

2.1.1 General Data Protection Regulation

The General Data Protection Regulation (GDPR), from Regulation (EU) 2016/679, provides “a set of standardised data protections laws across all member countries”, as stated in the REFLOW (D7.2 Data Management Plan). GDPR ensures ethical use of personal data and keeps personal data secured.

To ensure the data collection to be GDPR compliant, personal data collected during the primary data collection are pseudonymized. Personal Data are never disclosed, and access to the data collected are performed through the GDPR compliant SharePoint, selected by the REFLOW project to be the common platform for sharing data internally. The access is secured and only the consortium partners have access to the storage. Beta version of the Primary Data Collection Templates are implemented on the GDPR compliant Excel Microsoft Spreadsheets, as specified in the Data Management Plan. For the scope of the REFLOW project, this template has been implemented in the Pilot Cities Framework, a REFLOW tool for collecting data, to facilitate the data collection process for REFLOW pilots' cities. As recommended in the Data Management Plan to support accessibility, a “User Guide” (see Annex 1) is produced and made available on the SharePoint. According to the REFLOW Data Management Plan “All offline data that includes personal data will be digitalised and uploaded to the main storage system (SharePoint) as soon as possible by the researcher responsible of its collection. Once this is done, offline personal data must be destroyed” (D7.2 Data Management Plan).

2.1.2 Data quality & Data nature

Data collected within the scope of Growing Map of City Production Capacity and Material Flows are ranked among the Derived data in the REFLOW Data Management Plan (D7.2 Data Management Plan). Those are defined as data “including compiled data from other sources or case studies. It includes data derived from REFLOW’s online platforms, databases generated

after mining data or statistical analysis, toolkits or reports that use REFLOW’s generated data, among other types of data” (D7.2 Data Management Plan).

Some entities can reach a high level of details, while others are only able to hand over general data. This variability can be the results of several causes.

From the entity, it could be a consequence of the:

- lack of control over their activities
- lack of documentation and/or tracking
- lack of interest over their own data.

Moreover, the variability of the data can also be caused by the very essence of the entity interviewed and its primary activity, which can be radically different from one partner to another. Finally, the data collected can highly depend on the contact person interviewed within the entity. Their own bias (personal beliefs, personal affinities to sustainable development), their business and their level of technical understanding can interfere with the quantity and quality of information handed over. Concomitantly, the information that goes into too much detail will come up against data confidentiality.

Faced with this significant variability in accessible information, it was necessary to implement a data collection methodology that anticipates and includes these differences from the outset. The key words for this template must therefore be **flexibility and adaptability**.

The general shape of the template, generated on Excel SharePoint, is a spreadsheet presenting the different themes of data to collect. It aims to be used during interviews or during workshops, with the objective of filling in as much information as possible. Moreover, its self-explanatory form allows the template to be filled in and/or completed afterwards. The template has been first designed for the Paris pilot (see sub-chapter 2.2.1). Some close partners have been using the beta version and their feedback has enabled the PARIS team to improve the template. Each pilot specific template was updated and validated by the pilot cities and are presented in the section 3.1 Data collection specificities.

2.2 Building the template: information requirements

This part sums-up the preliminary information needed to create the template. The construction of the template is based on three major questions, and thus the following requirements:

Table 2: Template information requirements

Major question	Information required for building the template
- What is the subject of your data collection?	states of the material and transformation it can undergo

- What is the form of the data collected?	common unit used to handle the quantity of each pilot's material
- Why do you collect data?	stakes of each pilot's project

The stakes of the pilot's project direct the questions of the interview. The states of the material and its transformation forms lists that can easily be transformed into drop-down menus to frame and facilitate the filling of the template. Finally, the unit form list that prepares the data for further investigation and other work packages.

2.2.1 Template's test-case

A beta template created for the Paris pilot has been tested out for three close partners:

- FIAC: International art fair in Paris
- Morning Coworking Richelieu: coworking place in Paris, closed in 2019
- Restore: re-use workshop and coworking place in Paris

Three major questions were asked: What is the quantity of wood your entity is handling? Where is the wood handled coming from and in which proportion? Where are you sending your wood afterwards and in which proportion?

These questions are answered in the three-red box in the template in figure 1.

For each question, the partner was asked to give as much additional information as possible on the wood species, the wood transformations, the wood states etc.

Additional information is filled in the last row of every main question box in figure 1

Thanks to these first tests of the template on the Parisian partners, several points have been highlighted:

- When interviewing one stakeholder, the nature and the quality of the information collected are variable within the same category (in the category 'supplier', data filled from supplier A and supplier B will not be the same in nature or quality)
- confidentiality of the data, it is crucial to ask for the level of confidentiality of each data entered to be sure to be able to communicate on it. The data collected can be pseudonymized when used in global flows analysis. Confidential data is not used in any geographical representation of the flows, as anonymity cannot be ensured.
- Data collected are more qualitative than quantitative.

Nota Bene: Data was collected for each stakeholder, but is not published yet, and is thus not included in the report.

Figure 1 shows the Paris pilot's template that resulted from the beta version's feedback. The image has been divided in two parts for better visibility. The final version of the template for each pilot cities is shared in the REFLOW SharePoint.

Over one or several event.s/over a year

Wood's and ephemeral events' actors

Name : _____

Contact Person _____

Address: _____

Estimation of the quantity of wood used - (unit of your choice)

Main recovery sites/material suppliers:
 -specify proportion by supplier and by event if applicable (unit of your choice)
 -add additional product information if needed

Main destinations: collection of wood after use for recycling (up-cycling).
 - specify the proportion/quantity that is sent for reevaluation and by event if applicable (up-cycling)
 - specify the process undergone by the product
 - specify proportion by destination and by event if applicable (unit of your choice)
 - add additional information if needed

	event	E2	
Quantity of wood used	Unit ▾	additional information	
Supplier's name		Supplier 1	Supplier 2
Proportions	Unit ▾	number (choose the unit first)	number (choose the unit first)
Additional information		(state of the material, and additional information)	
Destination's name		Destination 1	Destination 2
Type of process		▾	▾
Specific processes		▾	▾
Proportions	Unit ▾	number (choose the unit first)	number (choose the unit first)
Additional information			

Figure 1: PARIS pilot's Template spreadsheet

The form and principles are then extended to the other pilots, with the objective of keeping a common **general form but with a pilot specific content**, to facilitate the **replicability**.

To generalize the template, a discussion has been initiated with all pilots to better understand their scenario. A first draft based on the beta version has then been presented to each pilot, on which they gave us feedback during workshops. Their feedbacks have then been implemented, and the results shared with them for validation.

2.2.2 Data Collection User Guide

To support the data collection process with the template, a data collection user guide was developed. This guide consists of both

- 1) an explanation of how to feed the data collected into the template, and
- 2) an interview guide. The interview guide includes a list of questions to ask to drive the interview into getting as much data as possible from each partner.

The data collection users guide has been developed for each pilot city integrating the adaptations of the template both in the user guide and interview guide.

The user guide can be found in the annex 2.

2.2.3 Pilots formation to the Data Collection

The Paris pilot team presented the data collection template in detail to each pilot city during a workshop. This workshop was held on MIRO and was used for entering an iterative feedback process for both the format and the content of the template, but also to present and familiarize each pilot the template. These sessions were also the time for a Q&A session with each pilot.

Figure 2 below shows a screenshot of the MIRO dashboard for the second workshop.

VEJLE PILOT DATA COLLECTION TEMPLATE

Actors in Plastic recycling				
Name:				
contact person:				
Address:				
Estimation of the quantity of plastic used - (unit of your choice)		unit	additional information	
ORIGIN Main recovery sites/material suppliers: - specify proportion by supplier (unit of your choice) - specify the type of plastic - add additional product information if needed		Supplier's name	Supplier 1	
		Proportion by supplier	unit	number (choose the unit first)
		Type of plastic		
		additional information	state of the material and additional information	
DESTINATION Main destinations of plastic after use - specify an treatment of plastic for each destination - specify proportion per customer (unit of your choice) - add additional information if needed		Destination's name	Destination 1	
		Type of plastic		
		Type of process		
		Specific process		
		Specific process		
		Proportions by destination	unit	number (choose the unit first)
		additional information		

3. Please complete the lists : "Unit" and "specific treatment" "type of plastic with any missing category"

unit	Treatment types	specific treatment	Types of plastic	state of the material
%	Up-cycling	Manual Sorting	PET/PETE	Object
weight (t)	Reuse	Depolluting	HDPE/PEHD	Powder
weight (kg)	Waste reclamation/recycling plant	Depolluting & Ferrous material removing	PVC	Extruded pellets
volume (m ³)	Manufacturing	Optical/Density/boyancy sorting	LDPE/LD	Flakes
surface (m ²)	Non-recovered	Shredding	PP	Polyester yarn
number	Collection and sorting process	Compressing	PS	Fiber
	Other	Sheet's compressing	PE	New Polymer
	Unknown	Shredding & melting into pallets	Other	Synthetic Fabric
		3D printing	Unknown	Filaments
		Heating and extruding into filaments		Other
		Melting, spinning and weaving		
		Chemical recycling		
		Pulversation into powder		
		Extruding into pellets		
		Other		
		Unknown		

4. How do you think the map and the data collection template could be of use for you ?

Figure 2: Workshop 2 - template presentation

2.2.4 Implementation of the template to the Pilot Cities Framework

As part of the REFLOW spirit to share forms on common tools, the template designed for each pilot city is being implemented on the REFLOW Pilot Cities Framework. As introduced earlier in this chapter, the Pilot Cities Framework, generated internally by WAAG, is being used to collect data. Implementing the data collection on this internal REFLOW tool allows a personalisation of the global layout of the data collection's form, as well as a better user-experience for the pilots. Moreover, data collected can directly feed the REFLOW Open Data Dashboard.

Open Data Dashboard developed within the REFLOW project is meant to be the visually appealing interface between the open data and the end-user. It allows pilot cities to implement their data and use publicly available open data and create their own dashboards to display their data. The city's pilots can then compose their dashboards using a specific selection of modules (charts, diagrams ...) to display their data.

Thanks to the work of the WAAG team, a specific data collection page is being created on the Pilot Cities Framework to be accessible by each REFLOW Pilot city.

Figure 3. Data collection material page on the Pilot Cities Framework

Each REFLOW pilot city have access to their specific questionnaire, with similar structure as in the spreadsheet template presented before, but in a more visual and user-friendly way to be used for data collection.

← DATA COLLECTION MATERIALS - AMSTERDAM

AMSTERDAM
PARIS
BERLIN
MILAN
VEJLE
CLUJ-NAPOCA

AMSTERDAM

The purpose of this interview is to obtain, at the end of the day, a representative idea of the material's journey entering and leaving your entity. The data you provide us is expected to be an estimate, for we are sensitive to the difficulties of evaluating exact quantities of incoming and/or outgoing material to and from your entity. The final goals of this process are to, first, have a global understanding of the material dynamics within the city, and second to uncover future business' opportunities within the city. The purpose of this interview is to obtain, at the end of the day, a representative idea of the material's journey entering and leaving your entity.

Who is the actor in the textile economy?

Name	Contact person	Adress
test	test	test

⊕

Estimation of the quantity of textile used - (unit of your choice)

We need an estimate of the total amount of textile collected/bought/received or the percentage of textile collected/bought/received out of a total amount of various materials. This quantity can be given in weight, volume or surface area.

Amount	Unit	additional information
12	▼	

⊕

Please specify the period of time on which those figures are valid.

What is the origin of the material (main recovery sites/material suppliers)?

Specify proportion by supplier (unit of your choice) and add additional product information if needed

Supplier Name	Amount	Unit	State Material
	1	▼	bla

⊕

What is the main destinations of textile after use?

- specify de treatment of the textile for each destination - specify proportion per customer (unit of your choice) - add additional information if needed

Destination Name	Type of process	Specific process1	Specific process2	Specific process3	Proportion by destination (number)	Proportion by destination unit	additional info

Figure 4: Data collection template of Pilot Cities Framework - Amsterdam page

This integration also ensures that the methodology is documented and easily accessible for all REFLOW members. Finally, the standardization of this process improves the sustainability of those results.

← DATA COLLECTION MATERIALS - AMSTERDAM

AMSTERDAM PARIS BERLIN MILAN VEJLE CLUJ-NAPOCA

BERLIN

Only Berlin should fill this in

Who is the actor?

Name	Contact person	Address

⊕

Please specify the period of time on which those figures are valid.

Please specify the estimation of the quantity of energy used to/that heat water (unit of your choice)

Amount	Unit	Additional information
	▼	

⊕

From which systems are the waste waters coming from ?

- heater
- households machine
- water system
- households appliance
- shower
- industrial sites and processes
- Office Buildings
- Other

What is the flow rate of wastewater - (unit of your choice)?

Amount	Unit	Additional information
	▼	

⊕

What is the temperature of wastewater - in average - (unit of your choice)?

Figure 5: Data collection page on the Pilot Cities Framework - Berlin page

← DATA COLLECTION MATERIALS - AMSTERDAM

AMSTERDAM
PARIS
BERLIN
MILAN
VEJLE
CLUJ-NAPOCA

PARIS

Only Paris should fill this in

Who is the actor in the wood's and ephemeral events?

Name	Contact person	Adress

⊕

What is the name of the event?

Estimation of the quantity of wood used - (unit of your choice)

We need an estimate of the total amount of wooden products collected/bought/received or the percentage of wooden products collected/bought/received out of a total amount of various materials.

Amount	Unit	additional information

⊕

Please specify the period of time on which those figures are valid.

What is the origin of the wood (main recovery sites/material suppliers)?

Specify proportion by supplier and by event if applicable (unit of your choice) and add additional product information if needed

Supplier Name	Amount	Unit	State Material	Additional information

⊕

What are the main destinations: collection of wood after use for recycling (up-cycling)?

Specify the proportion/quantity that is sent for revaluation and by event if applicable (up-cycling), the process undergone by the product, proportion by destination and by event if applicable (unit of your choice)

Destination Name	Type of process	Specific process1	Specific process2	Specific process3	Proportion by destination (number)	Proportion by destination unit	additional info

Figure 6: Data collection on the Pilot Cities Framework - Paris page

As can be seen on figure 4 and figure 5 and figure 6, the data collection pages have been personalized by each REFLOW pilot city, with different multiple-choice lists, but in a similar structure. Following the Excel SharePoint template presented before, each city template is built in a similar structure, to ensure replicability, but personalized to fit closer to each material flow specificities.

2.3 Methodology for implementing the mapping of the Material Flows Within a City

The mapping of the Material Journeys Within a City's final version will be implemented in the Open Data Dashboard, which is an open source REFLOW platform, used as an interface between REFLOW's data and the end users. Primary Data and data from the mapping collected from the Pilot Cities Framework introduced earlier will feed the Open Data Dashboard. Open Data Dashboard developed within the REFLOW project is meant to be the visually appealing interface between open data and the end-user. It allows pilot cities to implement their own open-data, and publicly available open data, and create their own dashboards to display their data. The city's pilots can then compose their dashboards using a specific selection of modules (charts, diagrams ...) to display their data. However, the Open Data Dashboard is not yet available. Hence, in the meantime, a beta version has been created.

From its description, the mapping of the Material Journeys Within a City must be **simple, transparent, and user-friendly and open source**. The map shall be as inclusive as possible. In particular, the colours will have to be adapted to a colour-blind public.

According to the description of the mapping of the Material Journeys Within a City description and needs, here are the technical task's needs:

- user friendly & inclusive (for the public)
- user friendly (for the other REFLOW partners to use and/or modify)
- easily accessible (web access)
- Data storage (extensible)

These needs can then be translated into different criteria for the software.

- strong community support
- turnkey solution: from the conception to the publishing online
- user-friendly
- aesthetic
- not too sophisticated

From the very beginning of this work, a benchmark has been continuously elaborated on mapping software's.

Power BI, from Microsoft, is a business analytics software. This software provides a user-friendly interface for end users to easily visualize data from their business activities. On a dashboard, end-users can create visuals, using as much data as they wish to, using different plug-in designed by Microsoft or the strong community. The variety in the visuals available on Power BI make it flexible. The dashboard, on which the end-user organizes its own layout of visuals, can be published online.

After the redesigning process, Power BI, has been found to be a relevant candidate for the mapping of the Material Journeys Within a City.

3. City level data collection

In short, here is the overall methodology built during this task.

First, the specificities of each pilot city (material and usages) must be defined, as well as their expectations and needs from the mapping of the Material Journeys Within a City. Second, the limits and boundaries of the mapping of the Material Journeys Within a City must be defined.

Following these steps, the relevant usages of the materials are listed, and the flow of materials are either up-streamed or down-streamed from the usages, depending on the pilot specificities. When necessary, to clarify life cycle material steps, interviews are held according to a specific data collection methodology (see chapter 2). The methodology is standardized for all pilot cities, but its content is adapted to each pilot. The principles are the same, but the detailed information is pilot-specific.

From the data collection, the flow of materials becomes clear enough to understand their possible journeys and sketch out their life cycle.

The data collected will be fed directly in the Open Data Dashboard from the REFLOW Pilot Cities Framework presented before, through an API connection once the Open Data Dashboard is launched. In addition to the data collected through the methodology, the data used in the development of the mapping of the material journey within a city will be available on the Open Data dashboard, along with an open-source visualisation module.

Six maps display the life cycle of the materials, one per material. The map sketches out the possible journeys of the material, before consumption, after consumption or both. Each map is integrated into a wider dashboard, with pilot-specific filters. A notice is also integrated into the dashboard, that explains to the user how to disclose the different material journeys: they can choose to see an overview, one journey at a time or using the filters.

The maps put into the spotlight possible journeys that are not widely known, highlight the positive environmental impacts of a circular journey, in order to understand the business opportunities offered by a circular economy and the high potential of what is considered as waste in the linear economy.

3.1 Data collection specificities

This part will present all the pilot-specific data collection templates. Each template was designed from the same structural basis and adapted to each city and material specificity.

Each template can be found in the annexes 2 to 7 from for better visibility.

3.1.1 Paris

Paris pilot mainly focuses on the ephemeral construction or event's organizer and their ecosystem. Tracking the material and identifying the added value of each actor is beneficial for the sake of the pilot. Figure 7 shows a screenshot of the Paris pilot data collection template. Data are collected about the material transiting through the entity, their origin, and their destination.

Wood's and ephemeral events' actors			
Name :			
Contact Person			
Address:			
Estimation of the quantity of wood used - (unit of your choice)	Quantity of wood used	Unit	additional information
Main recovery sites/material suppliers: -specify proportion by supplier and by event if applicable (unit of your choice) -add additional product information if needed	Supplier's name	Supplier 1	
	Proportions	surface (m²)	number (choose the unit first)
Main destinations: collection of wood after use for recycling (up-cycling). - specify the proportion/quantity that is sent for reevaluation and by event if applicable (up-cycling) - specify the process undergone by the product - specify proportion by destination and by event if applicable (unit of your choice) - add additional information if needed	Additional information (state of the material, and additional information)		
	Destination's name	Destination 1	
	Type of process		
	Specific processes		
	Proportions	Unit	number (choose the unit first)
	Additional information		

Figure 7: PARIS pilot data collection template

Here are the details of the information to be selected via the drop-down menus:

_unit of quantity of wood	_process type	_specific process	_material state
percentage (%)	not valorised	Grinding	Raw material
weight (t)	Collection/Sorting	Cutting	Object (treated)
weight (kg)	Reusing	Sanding	Object (raw)
volume (m ³)	Recycling	Planning	Litter
surface (m ²)	Up-cycling	Assembling	Soiled litter
number	Assembly/Manufacturing	Dismantling	Compost
	Mechanical Treatment	Surface treatment	Wooden parts
	Chemical Treatment	Autoclave	Wooden scraps
	Stocking	Hydrosolubles salts	Wooden chips
	Other	High Temperature Treatment	Wooden Pellets
	unknown	Carbonisation	Hog Fuel
		Other	Methane
		Unknown	Stable Floor
			Energy
			Particle Panels
			Paper pulp

Table 3: Drop down menu - Paris template

3.1.2 Berlin

Berlin pilot stakes are to raise awareness of their ecosystem about how valuable wastewater heat recovery or more generally heat recovery can be valuable. It is the occasion for them to onboard people with a general understanding of the possibilities generated by wastewater heat recovery. The template can then help their partner so create easily understandable data for communication purposes.

Name :			
contact person :			
Adress :			
Estimation of the quantity of energy used to/that heat water (unit of your choice)		€	▼
From which systems the wastewaters are coming from ?	heater, households machine, water system, hous		
Flow rate of wastewater - (unit of your choice)		unit	▼
Temperature of wastewater - in average - (unit of your choice) over specific period of time to specify		°C	▼

Figure 8: BERLIN pilot data collection template

Here are the details of the information to be selected via the drop-down menus:

_unit of power	_unit of flow rate	_unit of temperature	_energy state
%	m3	K	household appliances
kWh/year	L	°C	Industrial sites and processes
kWh/m ² .year	m3/s		wastewater heat
kJ	m3/h		heat recovered
€	m3/day		heat used
	kL/day		Losses
	kL/h		
	L/s		

Table 4: Drop down menu - Berlin template

3.1.3 Amsterdam

Amsterdam pilot stakes are to raise awareness about how valuable home textile wastes can become after being sorted and correctly discarded in the appropriate bin. Their pilot has an educational purpose. As such, the beginning is quite like the Parisian template with the coordinates, the general quantity and then the origin of the fabric handled by the entity. The real difference lies in the drop-down menus available.

Actors in the textile economy			
Name :	<input type="text"/>		
contact person :	<input type="text"/>		
Adress :	<input type="text"/>		
Estimation of the quantity of textile used - (unit of your choice)	<input type="text"/>	volume (m ³)	additionals informations (fabric s
ORIGIN Main recovery sites/material suppliers: -specify proportion by supplier (unit of your choice) -add additional product information if needed	Supplier's name		Supplier 1
	Proportions by supplier	unit	number (choose the unit first)
	additionals informations		(state of the material and other)
DESTINATION Main destinations of textile after use - specify de treatment of the textile for each destination - specify proportion per customer (unit of your choice) - add additional information if needed	Destination's name		Destination 1
	Type of process		▼
	specific process (when applicable)		▼
	specific process (when applicable)		▼
	specific process (when applicable)		▼
	Proportions by destination	unit	number (choose the unit first)

Figure 9: AMSTERDAM pilot data collection template

Here are the details of the information to be selected via the drop-down menus:

_unit of quantity if textile	_ type of process	_specific process	_ fabric state
% weight (t) weight (kg) volume (m ³) surface (m ²)	Up-cycling Reuse Fiber reclaiming Manufacturing Non-recovered sale Unknow	Specific process Unraveling Shredding Spinning Woven Energy recovery Fiber recovery Mechanical treatment Chemical Treatment Modification of textile waste Enzymatic hydrolysis of textile waste Extrusion (synthetic	Wearable Non wearable Second-hand High Quality Second-hand Strips Woven Non-woven Knitted Knitting clips Fabric roll Fabric scraps Yarn Thread Insulation

		fiber)	Stuffing Cleaning material Natural fiber Synthetic fiber Blended fiber Cashmere Cashmere knitting clips Cashmere yarn Cashmere thread Wool Combed wool Regenerated wool Angora wool Bio-chemical Bio-plastic Bio-surfactants
--	--	--------	---

Table 5: Drop down menu - Amsterdam template

fabric state table

Color	material	aspect	type
light	Animal based fiber	patterns	Second-hand High Quality
dark	Synthetic based fiber	plain	Bio-chemical
bright	Plant-based fiber	other	Bio-plastic
blue	Mineral-based fiber	both	Bio-surfactants
black	cashmere		Cleaning material
brown	Regenerated wool		Combed
green	Wool		Fabric roll
grey	Angora		Fabric scraps
orange	Linen		Insulation
pink	Cotton		Knitted
purple	other		Knitting clips
red	all		Non wearable
white			Non-woven
yellow			Regenerated Fabric
other			Second-hand

all			Second-hand clothing
			Strips
			Stuffing
			Thread
			Woven
			Yarn
			all
			other

Table 6: Drop down menu - Amsterdam template - fabric state table

3.1.4 Vejle

For Vejle and the topic of plastics, the data collection is like that for Amsterdam and Paris. Indeed, the same type of information is sought, and the same mapping process would be put in place. However, for plastics the information is collected more easily as it falls into 7 transparent and identifiable categories. The transformation processes are also more established and defined than for wood or textiles.

Actors in Plastic recycling						
Name :						
contact person :						
Address :						
Estimation of the quantity of plastic used - (unit of your choice)			unit	▼	additionnals informations	
ORIGIN Main recovery sites/material suppliers: - specify proportion by supplier (unit of your choice) - specify the type of plastic - add additional product information if needed	Supplier's name				Supplier 1	
	Proportion by supplier		unit	▼	number (choose the unit first)	
	Type of plastic				▼	
	additionnals informations				state of the material and additional Informations	
DESTINATION Main destinations of plastic after use - specify de treatment of plastic for each destination - specify proportion per customer (unit of your choice) - add additional information if needed	Destination's name				Destination 1	
	Type of plastic				▼	
	Type of process				▼	
	Specific process				▼	
	Specific process					▼
	Specific process					▼
	Proportions by destination		unit	▼	number (choose the unit first)	
	additionnals informations					

Figure 10: VEJLE pilot data collection template

Here are the details of the information to be selected via the drop-down menus:

_unit of quantity of plastic	_treatment type	_specific treatment	_type of plastic	_state of the material
% weight (t) weight (kg) volume (m ³) surface (m ²) number	Treatment types Up-cycling Reuse Waste reclamation/recycling plant Manufacturing Non-recovered Collection and sorting process Other Unknown	Sorting Depolluting Depolluting & Ferrous material removing Optical/Density/Buo yancy sorting Shredding Compressing Sheet's compressing Shredding & melting into pallets 3D printing Heating and extruding into filaments Melting, spurning and weaving Chemical recycling Pulverisation into powder Extruding into pellets Other Unknown	Types of plastic PET/PETE HDPE/PEHD PVC LDPE/LD PP PS PE Other Unknown	Object Powder Extruded pellets Flakes Polyester yarn Fiber New Polymer Synthetic Fabric Filaments Other

Table 7: Drop down menu - Vejle template

3.1.5 Cluj-Napoca

This template is only made for primary data collection and would help cities to take a step forward toward an exhaustive data collection. It will raise awareness about which type of data they need to gather and which type of problems they could encounter in their willingness to collect data: lack of information relative to the origin of the energy, lack of information about the energy consumption etc. This template highlights the origins of the energy, however the origin of the urban energy is not necessarily known, as it is the case for Cluj-Napoca. Hence the “origin” section needs to be answered only “when applicable”.

Cluj-Napoca pilot stakes are to raise awareness about energy consumption and circular economy. In this data collection, figure 11, the principal objective is hence to highlight the origins of the energy, whether it is fossil energy, renewable energy or nuclear.

Name :				
contact person :				
Adress :				
Estimation of the quantity of energy consumed - (unit of your choice)		m ³	additionnals informations	
PROVIDER List of the main energy provider when applicable	Provider's name	Provider 1	Provider 2	
	Energy state or form			
	Additional informations			
SOURCES List of the main sources of consumption - (unit of your choice)	Source of consumption	Source 1	Source 2	
	Proportion by source	unit		
	Additional informations	additionnals informations	additionnals informations	
Recommendations to reduce these sources' consumption / remarks about the improvements				

Figure 11: CLUJ-NAPOCA pilot data collection template

Here are the details of the information to be selected via the drop-down menus:

_unit of energy	_processes	_energy state	_energy from
% kWh/year lei m ³	Combustion Mechanical Energy to electricity Heat to mechanical Energy Solar Energy to electricity	Electricity Losses Wind mechanical energy Hydraulics' mechanical energy Solar Energy Renewable Energy Coal-fired power plant Fuel Energy Biogas Nuclear Energy Heat & Flue gas Heat & Radioactive waste	Heat Electricity

Table 8: Drop down menu - Cluj-Napoca template

3.1.6 Milan

Data collection can support the activity of Milan pilot by presenting the quantity of business opportunities created by valorizing food waste.

The quantity of food purchased, and the destination of waste and other materials are then needed to get an idea of the flow. The additional information is used to determine the condition of the food, the level of processing and the intended treatment process. In this way, an overview of the entire life cycle is obtained, from the seller to the up-cycling actor.

Name :				
contact person :				
Address :				
Estimation of the quantity of food sold - (unit of your choice)		unit	period of time	additionnals informations (the answer i
ORIGIN Main recovery sites/food suppliers: -specify proportion by supplier (unit of your choice) -specify the type of supplier -add additional product information if needed	Total of food bought/ acquired	Supplier's name	Supplier 1	
		Proportions	unit	number (choose the unit first)
		Period of time	period of time	period of time
	unit	Type of supplier	Type of supplier	Type of supplier
DESTINATION Main destinations of foodwaste, transformed or not - specify de treatment of the food for each destination - specify proportion per customer (unit of your choice) - add additional information if needed	Material state	Material State	Material State	
	additionnals informations		additional informations such as the type of food, the quality etc...	
	Destination's name	Destination 1	Destination 1	
	Type of process			
	Proportions	unit	number (choose the unit first)	
	Period of time	period of time	period of time	
	additionnals informations		additional informations such as the type of food, the quality etc...	

Figure 12: MILAN pilot data collection template

Here are the details of the information to be selected via the drop-down menus:

_unit of quantity of food	_type of process	_type of supplier	_material state	_period of time
% weight (t) weight (kg) number price (€)	composting Donation Biogas Disposal Farming Dumpster Diving Innovative up-cycling process other	Organic Small producer Industrial producer Vegan Vegetarian Reseller/Food traders Caterer Cooperative Association	Vegetable/fruits Energy Compost Leftovers Ugly Vegetables/fruits Biogas Leather-like material Recovery product Bioplastic	yearly monthly weekly daily trimestrial

		Collecting/sorting company General Food Market (Foody hub) Food Market Innovative up-cycling company Industrial Food company Specific Collecting/sorting company Peri-urban producer Urban producer other	Methane Fabrics Construction material Insulation other	
--	--	--	--	--

Table 9: Drop down menu - Milan template

3.2 Mapping of the Material Flows within a City

As explained earlier in the report, Power BI was used as a user-friendly tool to develop visuals, while the open data dashboard is in development. Once the Open Data Dashboard is available, the visuals will be created using this open-source tool. Hence, results for the mapping presented below have been realised under Power BI.

The plug-in used for the mapping is “PAFnow Process mining”. The annex 8 “Mapping technical documentation” presents, an extract of the spreadsheet used to create the following figures, as well as the corresponding screenshots of the PowerBI dashboard’s settings. Instructions about how to use this plug-in are also presented.

The map is integrated into a wider dashboard, where several other features help to understand the material life cycle, as visible in figure 13 below. The main feature is the map, at the center of the dashboard, displaying the different paths on the dashboard. This feature has been created using the plug-in “PAFnow process mining” of PowerBI. This plug-in allows, thanks to a progress toolbar at the bottom (display path one by one feature), allows to disclose the material journeys one by one. At the top right corner, another feature corresponding to a pilot-specific filter allows the user to display the paths depending on a specific parameter, for example, the type of process. This feature uses the plug-in ChicletSlicer of PowerBI. Finally, at the top left corner, a notice explains the user how to use the dashboard.

Figure 13: Description of the different part of the mapping

Before disclosing the mapping set-up for each result, and to clarify some points, the definitions of “re-use and second-hand asset”, “recycling”, “up-cycling”, “energy recovery” and “renewable energy” are reminded, using Ellen McArthur references when possible or other reliable references.

Re-use and second-hand asset, designate here, according to (*Definitions List*, n.d.): “Plant, property and equipment assets purchased second hand, whether or not they have been designed along circular economy principles.”

The **recycling** process is considered here as (*Definitions List*, n.d.) “The process of reducing a product all the way back to its basic materials, reprocessing those materials, and using them to make new products, components or materials. Recycling refers to materials that are processed in practice (as opposed to materials for which recycling is technically feasible).” As such, the composting process will be considered as recycling.

The **up-cycling** " is a process in which used materials are converted into something of higher value and/or quality in their second life. It has been increasingly recognised as one promising means to reduce material and energy use, and to engender sustainable production and consumption (Sung, 2015).

Energy recovery process is considered here as “the conversion of (non-recyclable) waste into usable heat, electricity, or fuel through a variety of processes, including combustion, gasification, pyrolysis, anaerobic digestion, and landfill gas recovery.” (*Energy Recovery, Fact Sheet*, 2015), considered as “Energy Recovery”.

According to the Ellen McArthur Foundation, “[energy] (electricity, heat, and fuel) is **renewable** if it is: • Non-biomass based renewable sources: [such as] Solar, Wind, Hydro (land-based, tidal, and wave), Geothermal, Biomass based energy must be a by-product of a process that primarily aims to recirculate nutrients (see qualifying conditions for nutrient recirculation). The biomass used must be:

- 1) sourced from regeneratively managed resources and derived from residues and/or by-products when using virgin material, or
- 2) processed from by-products/waste streams.” (*Definitions List*, n.d.)

In the following parts, each pilot city’s mapping of the Material Journeys Within a City’s is presented. Those mapping are specific to the material transformations happening in the pilot cities, presenting only transformations and processes that can be encountered within the city. However, those material journeys are generally representative of the material transformation that can happen in other location. Depending on their needs, for some pilot’s cities, a frequency occurrence to each path (see Amsterdam dashboard) has been added, to be able to see which paths are most likely to be followed by their material within their city.

Each mapping of the Material Journeys Within a City’s can be used as a starting basis for future cities focusing on the same material, to be completed and updated with city specific transformations. They also would be completed when new innovations on transformation processes are arising.

To disclose the material journeys within each Pilot, research has been conducted, supported by consultations with the Pilots to share documentations and knowledge. Each steps of the material lifecycle have then been further investigated through literature review –see references-.

The final information has then been checked and approved by each pilot. In particular, the metadata of the material processes and transformations, presented in the filters, have been chosen and filled by the pilot. Metadata are data that provides information about other data. For example, the journey occurrence frequency of a material is an information the frequency of the transformations process within the cities processes is a metadata, qualifying the transformations process itself. This will be further detailed pilot by pilot.

All mapping presented in part 3.2 can be found in annex 9 to 14 for better visibility. Please note that the online version of the document significantly drops the quality of the image displayed. If you have any troubles reading the figures, please consider downloading it for a better experience.

3.2.1. Mapping of the Wood Journeys within Paris

Description of the material journeys

To disclose the wood transformations and wood processes in Paris and build the mapping of the Wood Journeys Within Paris, consultation with the Paris pilot have been done to share documentation and knowledge. When specified, information presented in the following paragraphs are from external references.

Events or temporary construction often use wood as their primary material, as they are lighter and more easily transformable than other material.

Figure 14 displays all possible paths the wood can take within the Paris Pilot. This figure must be read from left to right. Each different color represents a different path and possibility within the Paris Pilot. The green point represents the wood lifecycle starting point. The first step is “raw wood”. The raw wood first goes through the manufacturing process, where the wood is transformed into parts or final furniture/objects. Then, the material is used by different actors, and goes either to temporary construction or events.

Once used, the wood is either discarded, stored, or re-used in situ/ex situ. Discarding the wood implies that the wood will either be recycled, used for energy recovery, or not valorised at all. **To the contrary, storing the wood offers many possibilities for re-use and up-cycling. These paths offer many business opportunities and are potential journeys the REFLOW project wishes to explore.**

Once discarded, according to the ADEME, the French Agency for Environment and Energy Management, the wood is discriminated into categories (Nicolleau et al., n.d.), depending on their treatment. When the wood is not treated (raw), it is grinded into specific sizes and the outcome, depending on their size, can be wooden chips and/or sawdust, or wooden pellets and/or compacted sawdust. The former one can then become either litter, stable floor, mulching or compost. The litter, once used, can also be turned into compost. The latter one, wooden pellets and/or compacted sawdust, are used as hog fuel. The material is burnt for energy recovery. Those are different ways to recycle wood (raw). When the wood is treated, it is also grinded into specific sizes, but the outcome is compressed into panels, to become OSB panels, MDF or chipboard.

To the contrary, **when wood is stored**, users have the opportunity to reuse it, as a **second-hand asset**. The wood re-enter its life cycle at the “use” step.

When the material is deteriorated, from the storage, the material **can undergo a reconditioning process, and re-enter its life cycle at the “use” step**. The reconditioning process can also precede a **re-manufacturing process**, during which the material is transformed again for a **second life**. Again, from this step, the material re-enters its life cycle at the “use” step.

Discover the different wood's journeys !

Disclose the wood possible paths using the progress tool bar at the bottom or/and the "type of process" filter at the top.

wood possible paths ●1 ●2 ●3 ●4 ●5 ●6 ●7 ●8 ●9 ●10

Figure 15 presents the wood journey that can be categorized as upcycling processes. Those transformations paths are critical, as they are adding value to the material once collected and are the paths on which the Paris pilot team is mostly focused, as well as re-use paths.

The pink link connecting the “remanufacturing” step back to the “use” step, is representative of the circularity as the material is going back into the loop.

Partners and actors interviewed all agreed on one tension point: storage is a critical link in the chain, as it mobilizes space for a certain duration, during which the wood does not yield any added value.

Figure 16 represents the paths of the wood journey in Paris that are categorized either as recycling path or up-cycling paths. Compared to Figure 15, it shows that there is way more processes related to the recycling of the wood, than its upcycling. It emphasizes the importance of developing upcycling processes, as after being upcycled and re-used, material could still be recycled, while having an increased life cycle.

In addition, upcycling processes are less documented, and little data is available, compared to the nationalized recycling processes.

3.2.2 Mapping of the Wastewater heat Journeys within Berlin

Berlin Pilot material journeys are simple to sketch-up as wastewater are feeding the Berlin’s sewage network, and that heat recovery needs specific technical installations to be effective. Indeed, wastewater heat can either be wasted (dissipated) in the sewer or recovered. The only parameters that need clarifications was on the moment of the chain the heat was effectively recovered. For that, primary research has been done to better understand the technology (see references). The clarification with Berlin Pilots has been conducted through a workshop. Finally, the text has been checked and approved by the pilot.

Description of the material journeys

Residential buildings, offices, or industries produce **hot or warm wastewater** that is discarded through the sewer system. This wastewater can be directly sent to a wastewater pumping station, from which it goes through a wastewater pressure pipe, for finally being sent to a wastewater treatment plant, which results in energy losses. After this process, the cleaned water is then sent back to a river a waterway or a body of water according to the Berliner Wasserbetriebe, the Berlins company in charge of the water waste system (*Wastewater*, n.d.).

On the contrary, the hot or warm wastewater can be a source of heat recovery if the wastewater goes through a **heat exchanger** (‘Unlocking the Potential of Renewable Energy Sources’, 2018), **preliminary installed in the sewer system**. There, the **heat extracted is recovered and can be sent to heat residential buildings, offices, or industries**.

Similarly, the heat exchanger can either be installed **after the wastewater pressure pipe or the wastewater treatment plant**. Berlin Pilot’s specified that the localisation of the heat exchanger in the chain **depends on various parameters**, such as the environment, the feasibility and the final purpose of the heat recovered.

The wastewater heat journeys for the Berlin pilot are displayed figure 17.

3.2.3 Mapping of the Textile Journeys within Amsterdam

Description of the material journey

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement number 820937.

The following paragraphs describe the possible post-consumer home textiles' journeys. They are all displayed figure 18 in the general layout of the home textile's states and transformation within the Amsterdam Pilot. The different paths showed by the mapping of the home textile Journeys Within Amsterdam are detailed.

Some specific features implemented on the current mapping dashboard allows some metadata to be shown: here material's data about the occurrence's frequency of its transformation within the Amsterdam pilot, and material's data about the type of journey taken (circular, linear, re-use).

Manufacturing processes produce home textiles that are being used, washed, and properly maintained, before being discarded. From the discarding process, three paths can be taken:

1) the textile can be incinerated to produce energy, but such a process produces flue gas and ashes as by-products. This process adds little value and significantly destroys the value (*Guidelines on the Interpretation of the R1 Energy Formula for Incineration Facilities Dedicated to the Processing of Municipal Solid Waste According to Annex II of Directive 2008/98/EC on Waste*, n.d.) that was put into it during fiber, yarn, and fabric production

2) home textiles can also be discarded at landfills, where the textile deteriorates producing legacy substances that pollute soil, water, and air over time

3) but home textiles, when discarded correctly in the appropriate textile collection's bins, can also be collected, and sorted in collection center. From this last step on, the discarded home textiles begin their sustainable journeys. The figure presents the possible processes the textile can take once collected appropriately.

Once collected, the textile is sorted into two categories: wearable and non-wearable. The wearable products are sent to **second-hand dealers**. High quality second-hand clothing remains in Holland (Western Europe), while the rest is sent to Eastern Europe and Africa and Asia (especially India).

As shown on the mapping of the home textile Journeys Within Amsterdam figure 19, when the “common path” filter is activated, non wearable products are commonly going through another sorting process, for nature discrimination into natural, synthetic, or blended textile. Separately, the textiles are washed and sorted again, for a type, fiber, and color discrimination. The “type” category refers to “woven” “non-woven”, or “knitted”. The “woven” and “non-woven” textiles are shredded (or parts), while the “knitted” textiles are unraveled. Products from both processes can then be sent into 3 different processes: mechanical recycling, chemical recycling, or extrusion (synthetic / thermoplastic fibers only).

From the **chemical and mechanical recycling**, the fiber recovered is used as non-woven (mainly technical applications for sound and thermal insulation) or spun, to create blended,

synthetic, or natural yarns. The yarns are then worked into woven or knitted textile or other products, that can then be sent for textile finishing (dyeing, printing, adding patterns etc.), **from where they return to a manufacturer to produce new home textile products.**

Another output of the shredding process can be insulation/ furniture padding or cleaning materials, sent to the industry.

Figure 20 presents the journeys of home textile that are categorized as circular, without any filtering on the frequency of occurrence. It is interesting to see how many circular paths are already implemented within the city.

A rarely seen chemical recycling is the **Enzymatic recycling** (B Steinacker et al., 2019) represented in the figure 21 as a journey from the “circular economy” within the “rare path” occurrence. Shredded textiles undergo a bioprocess to separate the natural components from the synthetic ones. The natural component is degraded into a liquid that can be further transformed into a bio-based product that feeds the industry, while the synthetic components remain as synthetic fiber. This synthetic fiber recovered is then unraveled, spun, and woven into a synthetic fabric that can then be sent for textile finishing (dyeing, printing, adding patterns etc.) **where they return to a manufacturer to produce new home textile.**

The **extrusion process** is different from the other types of recycling, as it is especially designed for synthetic (thermoplastic) fiber and polymer recovery. From the shredded synthetic fiber, the extrusion (heating and grinding process) produces polyester pellets. Those pellets can be used to produce synthetic yarns. This material can be sent for textile finishing (dyeing, printing, adding patterns etc.) **where they return to a manufacturer to produce new**

3.2.4 Mapping of the Plastics Flows within Vejle

Description of the material journeys

The mapping of the plastic's Journeys Within Vejle is presented Figure 22. Metadata are also presented on the figure 23 and 24, which shows the number of paths that only specific type of plastic may take.

Once their first purpose is fulfilled and plastic objects are thrown away, plastic's wastes are either directly sorted at home, or wrongly sorted into common trash or thrown in nature. When they are not sorted or when they are wrongly sorted, plastic wastes are normally sent with other residual wastes to incineration. Incineration **can be used for energy recovery but add little value to the waste treated and would rather make it drop** (*Guidelines on the Interpretation of the R1 Energy Formula for Incineration Facilities Dedicated to the Processing of Municipal Solid Waste According to Annex II of Directive 2008/98/EC on Waste, n.d.*).

To the contrary, when plastic wastes are correctly sorted and collected, several journeys can be taken, for plastic recycling or up-cycling (*Building Machines*, n.d.).

Once collected, the plastic goes through a sorting process, to remove objects that are not plastic-made and proceed to a primary plastic's family sorting. In this process, the material is distinguished from thermoplastic to thermosetting plastic. The former ones are the only recyclable plastic. The plastic is then depolluted and removed from any ferrous material. After this step, the depolluted plastic goes through another sorting process, that can either be an optical, density or buoyancy sorting. Plastic is also usually sorted by family and colour. The plastics objects already dispatched by family and colour are shredded into flakes.

From this, plastic state PET, PP, PE and PS flakes can be directly turned into new objects, using a compressor or a sheets' compressor (*Building Machines*, n.d.). Alternatively, the flakes can also be melted and extruded into filaments, for 3D printing purposes (*Filament Makers*, n.d.).

In this process, PET, PP, PE (Rosenheim et al., n.d.) and PS flakes normally go through a mechanical recycling process. The flakes are heated (at a plastic's family-dependent temperature) to soften the material and purify it, and then it is extruded. As a result, high quality pellets of respectively PET, PP, PE or PS (Maharana et al., 2007) are obtained. PET pellets can further be melted and turned into fiber. The PET fiber is then spined and weaved into synthetic fabric (*Recycling of Plastic Bottles into Yarn & Fabric*, 2014).

For PP and PE flakes, a chemical recycling process is also a possible journey: the polymer structure is broken and regenerated as a **new plastic**.

Figure 22 shows the general new layout of the map. Figure 23 shows all the paths PET can go through and figure 24 all the paths PE can go through.

As can be seen on figure 23, PET flakes can also be pulverised into a fine powder to be used in **plastic manufacturing**.

Figure 24 show all possible path for PE plastic products, as shampoo bottles. The filters present commons household objects that are made of specific type of plastic, to help users understand the mapping.

Discover the possible journeys of plastic wastes in Denmark

Path number ● 1 ● 2 ● 3 ● 4 ● 5 ● 6

To disclose more paths, use the progress advancement toolbar at the bottom, and the plastic type filter on the right

Zoom 1

Zoom 2

Click on the plastic type to disclose their specific journeys

- PE (shampoo bottle)
- PET (bottles)
- PP (lunch box)
- PS (yoghurt cup)

©paf

Figure 24: Plastic's journeys using the "PE" filter

3.2.5 Mapping of the Urban Energy Journeys within Cluj-Napoca

Humans use three types of energy sources to produce electricity, heat, and light: fossil energies, renewable energies, and nuclear energy. Figure 25 displays the different paths of those energies in the Romanian energy network. Indeed, according to the International Energy Agency (IEA) (*Romania*, 2018) Romania energy is coming from those three types of energy sources.

Historically the most common fossil energy source in Romania, the coal-fired power plant, has been decreasing for the last couple of years with comparison to the fuel power plant, according to the IEA (*Romania*, 2018). Coal is burnt through a combustion process, from where three types of material are created: heat, flue gas and ashes.

Heat is then transformed into mechanical energy which is again transformed into electricity, while flue gas and a part of the ashes are released into the ambient air.

Fuel energy follows the same path. The fuel is burnt through a combustion process that creates heat, flue gas and ashes. Heat is transformed into mechanical energy, while flue gas and a part of the ashes are released into the ambient air.

Figure 26 presents all renewable energies used in Romania. They are biomass', hydro's and pico hydro's, wind, and solar energies.

In the renewable energies group, presented figure 26, biogas from the fermentation of biomass follows the same path as fossil energies. Although biogas releases flue gas and ashes in the ambient air, the main advantage of such a solution remains in the independence from the fossil energies it provides.

When rivers are available, dams make it possible to exploit the stored mechanical energy. The river is separated by the dam, with the water level being higher upstream than downstream. When opening the dams, the water naturally flows from the highest level to the lowest, activating hydraulics' turbines that transform mechanical energy into electricity. However, smaller installations are also available to exploit hydraulics' mechanical energy: micro/pico hydro power plants. Using the natural flow of rivers, micro or pico hydro power plants transform hydraulics mechanical energy into electricity.

Wind and solar energy are the least represented source of energy in Romania, according to the IEA (*Romania*, 2018). The breath of wind can also be exploited in a wind turbine, that transforms wind mechanical energy into electricity. Solar energy works differently as it needs photovoltaic panels to transform light (electrons) into electricity.

Finally, Nuclear energy produces heat and radioactive waste. The heat is then transformed into mechanical energy which is then transformed into electricity.

The different source of Energy within the city

Disclose the different journeys the urban energy can take, from sources to electricity, through the progress toolbar at the bottom and the type of energy sources' filter at the top. Zoom in and out on the diagram using the tools at the bottom left corner.

Select an Energy source

Fossil Energy

Nuclear Energy

Renewable Energy

Path Number ● 3 ● 5 ● 6 ● 7 ● 8 ● 9

Zoom 1

Zoom 2

Figure 26: Energy journeys using the filter “renewable energy”

This project has received funding from the European Union’s Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement number 820937.

3.2.6 Mapping of the Food leftovers Journeys within Milan

Farming processes produce fruits and vegetables that are sold into the food market after transiting through the general Milan food market (Foody Hub managed by So.Ge.Mi.). Two categories can be sold: conventional **vegetables/fruits and the “ugly vegetables/fruits”** (ortaggi brutti), sold as such as they do not fit in the aesthetic description of the conventional ones.

Foody Hub hosts wholesalers who intend to sell vegetables and fruits products to shops, restaurants, open market operators and traders of the 23 Municipal covered markets. Therefore, in the food journey from production to consumption, there are **two moments of food waste production**: at the Food hub during the exchange between wholesalers and resellers, and, considering the specific target group studied by the Milan pilot in REFLOW, in the municipal covered markets with final consumers (neighborhoods citizen).

The remaining unsold fruits and vegetables usually become leftovers. From this point, the leftovers can take several different paths. The most common one is the one where **leftovers are discarded and are thrown away to feed landfills**, where they deteriorate while producing methane. Several other options exist to **prevent wasting leftovers**

One of the most common ways to make use of leftovers is by **composting** them. This process produces two types of products that can be useful: **compost and biogas**. Biogas has a potential to be burnt through a combustion process, **to create energy**.

Innovative companies have been creating other solutions, consisting in collecting and sorting the leftovers by type and selecting the ones with the most interesting characteristics. As such, **coffee leftovers can be burnt to produce energy** (CEstakeholderEU, 2019), some fruits leftovers can be transformed into, other leftovers can be used for (Agralooop BioFibre™ *The NEW Natural Fiber*, 2019; *Food Waste as Raw Material for 3D Printed Bioplastics*, n.d.; *In Rotterdam Unsold Fruit Becomes Fake Leather*, 2019).

Figure 27 shows the general layout of the map for vegetable and fruits leftovers recovery. A filter, on the top right corner of the map, allows the user to disclose the paths corresponding to, respectively “Up-cycling”, “Recycling”, “Not Valorised”, “Unchanged”, “Energy Recovery” processes. The paths “Unchanged” are meant for fruits and vegetables that are not transformed after being discarded. Rather, as previously explained, they can be either donated, collected (Dumpster Diving), or sold.

Discover the possible journeys of fruits and vegetables wastes

Disclose the different food leftovers possible journeys, using the progress bar tool at the bottom or using the type of process' filter on the right. Zoom in and out on the diagram using the tools at the bottom left corner.

Select a type of process to disclose the different food waste journeys

Zoom 1

Zoom 2

Figure 27: General Layout of the fruits/vegetables leftovers' states and transformations within the Milan Pilot

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement number 820937.

Figures 28 and 29 show the effect of such a filter on the map. When the only “up-cycling” or “unchanged” respectively filter is selected, the only paths corresponding to them are disclosed. As can be seen in figure 28, Milan pilot city has identified many different innovative up-cycling transformations that are adding value to the fruits and vegetables wastes, as transforming it into bioplastic or fabrics for example.

Figure 29 shows the different transformation process that do not change the state of the fruit of vegetable. Most of it is sold directly in the markets, and the when not modified, leftovers are either donated or discarded.

Figure 29: Fruits/Vegetable leftovers' journeys using the "unchanged" filter

3.3 Uses and possible improvements

In this part, current and future use cases and possible improvements of the mapping and template are summarized by pilot cities.

As explained previously in this report, the current results will be implemented within the Open Data Dashboard. This will represent a major improvement of the result, as they will finally be open source. However, the implementation of the result as an open data resource is beyond the scope of this deliverable as the work done here extends

One of the main improvements for the mapping and template is the integration within the Open Data Dashboard currently being developed by REFLOW partners. This will allow the data and results to be open source.

The data being stored in the REFLOW Pilot city Pilot Cities Framework and on the REFLOW SharePoint will feed directly in the Open Data Dashboard through an API connection. Both the data used in the mappings and the data collected by each pilot cities through the templates will be included in this open-source tool. Material flow journeys will be redesigned using a visualisation module directly on the Open Data Dashboard as soon as available.

3.3.1 Paris

The map highlights the added value of the REFLOW project. With the recirculating loops of the “re-use” or “up-cycling” paths, it becomes clear how re-using material can be beneficial on an economic scale (added value) and on a social scale (reconditioning and re-manufacturing are business opportunities with high level skills). To the contrary, the linear paths show how recycling or energy recovery drop the value of the material. The fact that storage has been put at the same level as manufacturing for instance, sends a strong message. It shows how this process is important in life cycle.

Ultimately, it can raise awareness among the ecosystem about the value of their data.

One way to improve the map would be to develop a bit further the stockage processes and the re-manufacturing, to highlight even more the REFLOW added value.

3.3.2 Berlin

The map offers a good basis on which the Berlin Pilot could rely on for educational purposes. This kind of graphical design is indeed interesting to introduce students to the concept of heat recovery in the sewage system. Wastewater heat recovery can intervene at several steps of the wastewater system, whether it is directly in the sewage or after the pumps. It is important to have a basic sketch of the possibilities to introduce the subject.

The template will help Berlin Pilot to onboard potential new partners with the concept, using a representative data set as an example into the template. It will be valuable for face-to-face conversation with partners when the concept of recovering wastewater heat is explained, allowing future partners to understand more concretely the value of this process.

3.3.3 Amsterdam

The mapping helps the Amsterdam pilot to have a clear overview on the current status of the textile field. The filtering features are a good way to put in the spotlight the value of circular economy compared to traditional economy. Thus, it is useful for communication purposes regarding discussion with the municipality and stakeholders, to push a whole city towards a circular economy. Moreover, the way the map is constructed puts the recycling branch at the center of the discussion. The map highlights with another perspective the home textile life cycle, putting the recycling journeys at the center. The map allows home textile recycling’s stakes at the center of the attention. Such a map can sow the seeds of innovative ideas among stakeholders and raise awareness about home textile recycling. As such, it is a:

- Way to map out (needed) stakeholders in the recycling industry
- a way to map out how the recycling relates to current flow (on the map the different “routes” are visualised)

- a way to understand “leaks” in the current stream, towards circularity.

For future cities, the mapping is going to be a great first approach to the circular economy of the material they are interested in. It helps to set the first steps with REFLOW OS, understanding who part of the users could be, what goes where and what do they sell to each other. REFLOW OS is an economic network that encourages the development of a municipal circular economy. To the difference with a market place, one of the core aspects of an economic network is being able to create the flow that materials and activities create together in a specific period of time. It can be used for the development of a roadmap and strategy. It is a valuable input for the development of a circular blueprint for a city.

The interview is an important addition for Cities’ Circular Action Plans - replicability of the pilots, as a process is designed, tested and shared as a step for future cities. The interview can be used to reach out to possible stakeholders.

3.3.4 Vejle

The map visuals are a relevant support to display the overall paths plastic wastes can undergo after being discarded. Especially during Vejle pilot’s online events for dissemination of information to the general public, the map could support communication activities or help the pilot to raise awareness about the value of plastic wastes.

This is relevant for REFLOW stakeholders such as Municipality, Vejle’s test sites and, more generally, citizens.

To improve the visual, as it has been uncovered during the research about the plastic transformations and the discussions with the Vejle team, some national laws exist about plastic’s transformation. As such, it might be relevant in the future to add an additional feature, filtering the possible paths by countries, representative of the multitude of Plastic recycling’s regulation in the European Union.

3.3.5 Cluj-Napoca

The map is a good educational support to raise awareness about the possible origins of urban electricity or heat. Unfortunately, it is impossible to know, in Romania, the origin of the energy used, as the electricity produced country-wide feeds one only network at the national level, feeds the entire electrical system due to legal regulations. They all merge together, and the only information accessible would be the percentage of each origin nationally. Primary Data collection are needed in case when no data are primarily available in a standardized form. However, in the case of Cluj-Napoca, the solely energy transmission and system operator (the entity responsible with transporting energy) is public (*Electricity Regulation in Romania: Overview*, n.d.). On top of that, as previously explained, the detail of the energy sources cannot be accurately known. As such, all data collected in term of origins are similar and the solely difference remain in the consumption. However, Cluj-Napoca already have access to the

databases of the building they are studying. Therefore, Cluj-Napoca pilot does not plan on using the template.

A good feature to add in the future would be the differentiation between energy that is used as heat, and energy that is used as electricity.

3.3.6 Milan

The map becomes useful to represent potential uses of food waste based on the scenarios that the Milan Pilot is developing. Each scenario must be verified with main REFLOW Milan stakeholders (e.g. So.Ge.Mi or Amsa) and can activate additional minor stakeholders interested in the prototyping process (e.g. fab labs, farmers, market traders, circular start-ups).

Considering the previous activities about hands-on analysis at market levels, the Milan Pilot team intends to insert the data obtained through direct interviews and systematize them in the template for an overview of the market's flows. The template can be replicated for the 5 markets analyzed and for each market the food flows of the different traders can be shortly shown. Another use of the template is to collect further data from the big players recently engaged in the project such as So.Ge.Mi¹ and Amsa², identifying specific flows (food waste or agri-food for sale) from producers to consumers.

As a way for improvements, the map could discriminate the food journeys' ending point (green dot) by type of final consumption. For instance, all the paths that end by energy recovery would be terminated by one green dot, while all the paths that end by consumption of unchanged product would be terminated by another green dot.

¹ <https://www.sogemispa.it/>

² <https://www.amsa.it/en/cittadini>

4. Conclusion

For each pilot city, a mapping of the Material Flows within a City and a primary data collection methodology have been implemented.

As explained in the introduction, the results are broken down into two parts. First, an **interview-based methodology** for data collection to be used both by pilot cities and by future cities joining the circular economy movement. Second, **a mapping of the different processes of material's states and transformations** that the material studied can encounter throughout its life cycle for each REFLOW pilot cities.

The data collection process is based on interviews of key actors of the material lifecycle to identify the flows of material passing by the actors and clarify blurred points on the material life cycle. An interview guide for data collection has been developed to support the actor in the process. The information collected during this process feeds the data collection template. This template is designed to be **flexible, user friendly and adapted to different levels of granularity of information**. It can be filled with very little information, as with great details when accessible. It serves as the **first basis of data collection**, for a city to get visibility on the material flow and start identifying sources and gaps of data to work on.

The mapping of the material transformation is made through literature review to develop the backbone of the mapping and completed through feedback from the pilot city experts. This allows to have **clear visibility on the different transformations possible for the material**, as well as **identify opportunities from processes that are not used locally**. It can also be used as **communication support, to raise awareness** on different options for materials transformation and circular economy, and to **support lobbying activities**.

The results are to be used by themselves as stand-alone solutions but could also be connected to other tasks and work-packages of REFLOW and the replicable transition process that is being developed within the project. They offer a **first level understanding work for other work-packages**, enhance the understanding of the material journeys and are a way to **organize data** and are one of the **first steps in working towards the development of a circular city blueprint**.

More precisely, this task is supporting the following aspects of the REFLOW project:

Understanding of the ecosystem and the identification of potential business opportunities through the mapping, by providing an initial vision of the current situation, and visibility on existing processes that are not currently implemented in the location studied.

The development of the data collection methodology is **supporting the MFA process**, as it offers a first level of understanding and preliminary data to be used and complemented when

deep diving into the MFA process. This level of data is not sufficient to develop an MFA, but it offers a solid basis to use as a starting point.

The data collection methodology is also supporting the **replicability** of the REFLOW process to future cities. By documenting the process used to create the template, the challenges associated with the data collection, and providing both an interview guide and a modular template, the Paris Pilot team is giving future cities the tools to start their circular journey through data collection to identify key focus areas.

The actors and processes identified through the mapping can be used as first steps to define possible users of the **REFLOW OS**. The interactions between each user and the understanding of their individual needs can be taken into account during the further development and customization of REFLOW OS. It also provides a structure for the database, of what goes where, and what do they sell to each other.

The dataset generated from the data collection process and the mapping created for each pilot will be implemented in the **Open Data Dashboard** to be accessible to other cities.

The data collection template will be implemented in the **REFLOW Pilot Cities Framework** to be easily accessible for each REFLOW pilot city, in a user friendly and graphical way. It also allows us to keep track of the data collected and have it all been stored in the same place. This ensures that the work done by the pilots is kept for the future and can be built on.

The mapping can be used as a communication device with key partners to raise **awareness** on the circular economy and the opportunities related to the material studied. In that view, it can also be used as a support for **lobbying**.

The mapping is showcasing the current situation regarding material journey, which is pretty much linear. A next step is to represent the material journey that we want to reach, as a **circular journey**, starting from the current mapping. This will allow a better visualization of what pilots are working on, and what are the changes REFLOW pilots are going towards.

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ANNEXES

Annex 1: Data collection user guide

This guide is intended to assist in the completion of data collection using the file PILOT_data_collection_V.2. The instructions here are indicative and serve the sole objective of supporting the interviewer.

Start the interview

The purpose of this interview is to obtain a representative idea of the material's journey entering and leaving your entity.

The data you provide us are expected to be estimates, as we are sensitive to the difficulties of evaluating exact quantities of incoming and/or outgoing material to and from your entity.

The final goals of this process are to, first, have a global understanding of the material dynamics within the city, and second to uncover future business' opportunities within the city.

1. Paris Pilot

First, we would need an estimate of the total amount of wooden products collected/bought/received or the percentage of wooden products collected/bought/received out of a total amount of various materials. This quantity can be given in weight, volume, or surface area.

Please specify the period of time on which those figures are valid.

We will then try to define the wood journey by drawing up a non-exhaustive list of your main suppliers and the destinations of your product.

Origins of your wooden products

Do you have an idea of your main wood suppliers or the localisation of the wood deposit? Could you specify the type of supplier?

[repeat for each supplier]

Does the list seem complete enough?

Now could you tell us an estimate of the percentage or quantity of wood retrieved from each of your suppliers? If possible, specify the material's state received from this

supplier.

Do you have any further information about the collected wood, that is not available in the multiple choice above or further details about the wood retrieved from this supplier?

[repeat the process for each supplier]

Destination of your wooden products

Once going through your entity, what are the entities to which your wooden products are sent to?

Do you have an idea of the type of processes realised in this entity? Or what they collect your wooden products for?

Does the list seem complete enough?

Now could you tell us an estimate of the percentage or quantity of wood sent to each of your destinations? If possible, specify the material's state delivered to this destination.

[repeat for each destination]

If you have any feedback on this template or further details, do not hesitate to let us know.

2. Amsterdam Pilot

[pre-fill in the company name, address, and contact person details].

First, we would need an estimate of the total amount of textile collected/bought/received or the percentage of textile collected/bought/received out of a total amount of various materials. This quantity can be given in weight, volume, or surface area.

Please specify the period of time on which those figures are valid.

We will then try to define your textile journey by drawing up a non-exhaustive list of your main textile suppliers and your main products' destinations.

Origins of your textile

Do you have an idea of your main textile suppliers or the localisation of the textile deposit? I suggest you dictate their names to me.

Does the list seem complete enough?

Now could you tell us an estimate of the percentage or quantity of textile from each of your suppliers? If possible, specify the material's state received from this supplier.

Do you have any further information about the collected textile not available in the multiple choice above or further details about the material retrieved from this supplier?

[repeat the process for each supplier]

Textiles' destination

Once going through your entity, what are the entities to which your textile's products are sent? Do you have an idea of the type of processes realised in this entity? Or what they collect your textile for?

Does the list seem complete enough?

Now could you tell us an estimate of the percentage or quantity of textile sent to each of your destinations? If possible, specify the material's state delivered to this destination.

[repeat for each destination]

If you have any feedback on this template or further details, do not hesitate to let us know.

3. Berlin Pilot

First, we would need an estimate of the quantity of energy used to heat water, using the unit of your choice.

Please specify the period of time on which those figures are valid.

We will then try to define the energy journey by drawing up a non-exhaustive list sources of wastewater

From which system the wastewaters are coming from? Is it a household appliance, cooling system, heating system ...?

What is the flow rate of the wastewater? Please select the unit.

What is the average wastewater temperature?

4. Cluj-Napoca Pilot

First, we would need an estimate of the total amount of energy consumed by your building. This quantity can be given in lei, kwh, m³.

Please specify the period of time on which those figures are valid.

We will then try to define the energy journey by drawing up a non-exhaustive list of your main providers and the source of consumptions.

Origins of your energy

Do you have an idea of your main energy supplier?

Could you specify the type of energy your provider is supplying you with?

Can you give us further information about this provider? Did you engage specific procedures with them to improve your energy consumption?

[repeat the process for each supplier]

Does the list seem complete enough?

Energy Consumption

What are the main sinks of energy consumption in your buildings? How did you decrease their consumption or how are you planning on decreasing it? Do you have any remarks on this installation?

[repeat for each sink]

Does the list seem complete enough?

If you have any feedback on this template or further details, do not hesitate to let us know.

5. Vejle Pilot

First, we would need an estimate of the total amount of plastic-made products collected/bought/received or the percentage of plastic-made products collected/bought/received out of a total amount of various materials. This quantity can be given in weight, volume or surface area.

Please specify the period of time on which those figures are valid.

We will then try to define the plastic journey by drawing up a non-exhaustive list of your main suppliers and the destinations of your product.

Origin of the plastic

Do you have an idea of your main plastic suppliers or the localisation of the plastic deposit?

Could you specify the type of supplier?

Does the list seem complete enough?

Now could you tell us an estimate of the percentage or quantity of plastic retrieved from each of your suppliers? If possible, specify the material's state received from this supplier.

Do you have any further information about the collected plastic, that is not available in the multiple choice above or further details about the plastic retrieved from this supplier?

[repeat the process for each supplier]

Destination of your plastic products

Once going through your entity, what are the entities to which your plastic-made products are sent? Do you have an idea of the type of processes realised in this entity? Or what they collect your plastic-made products for?

Does the list seem complete enough?

Now could you tell us an estimate of the percentage or quantity of plastic sent to each of your destinations? If possible, specify the material's state delivered to this destination.

[repeat for each destination]

If you have any feedback on this template or further details, do not hesitate to let us know.

6. Milan Pilot

First, we would need an estimate of the total amount of food collected/bought/received or the percentage of food collected/bought/received out of a total amount of various materials. This quantity can be given in weight, volume, or surface area.

Please specify the period of time on which those figures are valid.

We will then try to define the food journey by drawing up a non-exhaustive list of your main suppliers and the destinations of your product.

Origin of the food

Do you have an idea of your main food suppliers or the localisation of the food deposit?
I suggest you dictate their names to me.

Could you specify the type of supplier?

Does the list seem complete enough?

Now could you tell us an estimate of the percentage or quantity of food retrieved from each of your suppliers? If possible, specify the material's state received from this supplier.

Do you have any further information about the collected food, that is not available in the multiple choice above or further details about the food retrieved from this supplier?

[repeat the process for each supplier

Leftovers' destination

We are now focusing on the food's leftovers. Could you give us a rough idea of the quantity or the proportion of leftovers you have? Could you please specify the period of time these figures are valid?

Once going through your entity, what are the entities to which your food's leftovers are sent to? Do you have an idea of the type of processes realised in this entity? Or what they collect your food's leftovers for?

Does the list seem complete enough?

Now could you tell us an estimate of the percentage or quantity of food's leftovers sent to each of your destinations? If possible, specify the material's state delivered to this destination.

[repeat for each destination]

If you have any feedback on this template or further details, do not hesitate to let us know.

End of interview

Thank you for taking the time to answer our questions.

If you still have time, we would like to hear back from you on this form:

what do you think about it?

How did you find this interview?

What would you advise us?

What improvements would you think it would be appropriate to make?

We are open to the discussion.

Annex 2 - template Paris

Wood's and ephemeral events' actors		
Name :		
Contact Person		
Address:		
Estimation of the quantity of wood used - (unit of your choice)		
Main recovery sites/material suppliers: -specify proportion by supplier and by event if applicable (unit of your choice) -add additional product information if needed		
Main destinations: collection of wood after use for recycling (up-cycling). - specify the proportion/quantity that is sent for revaluation and by event if applicable (up-cycling) - specify the process undergone by the product - specify proportion by destination and by event if applicable (unit of your choice) - add additional information if needed		
Quantity of wood used	Unit ▾	additional information
Supplier's name	Supplier 1	
Proportions	surface (m²) ▾	number (choose the unit first)
Additional information	(state of the material, and additional information)	
Destination's name	Destination 1	
Type of process	▾	
	▾	
Specific processes	▾	
	▾	
Proportions	Unit ▾	number (choose the unit first)
Additional information		

Annex 3 - template berlin

Name :			
contact person :			
Adress :			
Estimation of the quantity of energy used to/that heat water (unit of your choice)			
From which systems the wastewaters are coming from ?			
Flow rate of wastewater - (unit of your choice)			
Temperature of wastewater - in average - (unit of your choice) over specific period of time to specify			
	€	▼	<i>additionnals informations average tempera</i>
<i>heater, households machine, water system, households appliance, shower, industrial sites an</i>			
	unit	▼	<i>additionnals informations</i>
	°C	▼	<i>additionnals informations</i>

Annex 4- template Amsterdam

Actors in the textile economy		
Name :		
contact person :		
Adress :		
Estimation of the quantity of textile used - (unit of your choice)		
ORIGIN <i>Main recovery sites/material suppliers:</i> -specify proportion by supplier (unit of your choice) -add additional product information if needed		
DESTINATION <i>Main destinations of textile after use</i> - specify de treatment of the textile for each destination - specify proportion per customer (unit of your choice) - add additional information if needed		

	volume (m ³)	additionnals informations (fabric s
Supplier's name		Supplier 1
Proportions by supplier	unit	number (choose the unit first)
additionnals informations		(state of the material and other)
Destination's name		Destination 1
Type of process		▼
specific process (when applicable)		▼
specific process (when applicable)		▼
specific process (when applicable)		▼
Proportions by destination	unit	number (choose the unit first)

Annex 8 - Mapping technical documentation

The mapping dashboard created uses two plug-ins in Power BI: the principal one, Pafnow process mining, displays the life cycle, while the chiclet Slicer creates the filters.

First, the general features of PowerBI will be exposed. Then a spreadsheet about the wood life cycle material will be presented as an example along with its dashboard. The settings of the mapping plug-in will also be presented. Afterwards, the filter spreadsheet and the

General features of the PowerBI dashboard are visible figure A.

When opening PowerBI, the user must first link a spreadsheet to the dashboard. The data that the user wishes to visualise must be stored in a spreadsheet table beforehand. The first framed button “Excel”, at the top left corner of figure A serves that purpose. Once download, the user might select a “Visualisation” plug-in. Here, in the dashboard, we chose Power now process Mining and chiclets, the two icons framed in red on the panel “visualisations” on the right. To make it more appealing and self-explanatory, the user can add text on the dashboard.

The user can also choose to add several tabs to have several different boards available within the same dashboard. Here, the tab “wood” is displayed” (bottom left corner).

Figure A: General features of the Power BI dashboard

The main feature of this dashboard is the life cycle map. This plug-in (PAFnow process mining) has been created using table A as the input. Three categories have been used: ID_PARIS; Activity PARIS; and time_PARIS. The ID_PARIS gathers all “Activity_PARIS” of the same life cycle under the same identification. All ID_PARIS =1, for instance, represents one and only path. The last column, Business Opportunities, has been created to feed the

filter “chiclet”. Each “Activity_PARIS” are attributed a kind of business opportunity: recycling, not valorised, up-cycling, re-use, energy recovery.

Table A: extract of the PARIS spreadsheet for the POWERBI visuals.

ID_PARIS	Activity_PARIS	time_PARIS	Business Opportunities
1	Raw wood	1	Not valorised
1	Manufacturing	2	Not valorised
1	Use (Event organizer or Ephemeral Construction)	3	Not valorised
1	Discarding	4	Not valorised
1	Air, water and earth pollutants	5	Not valorised
3	Raw wood	1	Re-Use
3	Manufacturing	2	Re-Use
3	Use (Event organizer or Ephemeral Construction)	3	Re-Use
3	Storage	4	Re-Use
3	Second-hand	5	Re-Use
3	Use (Event organizer or Ephemeral Construction)	6	Re-Use
4	Raw wood	1	Up-Cycling
4	Manufacturing	2	Up-Cycling
4	Use (Event organizer or Ephemeral Construction)	3	Up-Cycling
4	Storage	4	Up-Cycling
4	Refurbishing	5	Up-Cycling
4	Use (Event organizer or Ephemeral Construction)	6	Up-Cycling

5	Raw wood	1	Up-Cycling
5	Manufacturing	2	Up-Cycling
5	Use (Event organizer or Ephemeral Construction)	3	Up-Cycling
5	Storage	4	Up-Cycling
5	Refurbishing	5	Up-Cycling
5	Re-Manufacturing	6	Up-Cycling
5	Use (Event organizer or Ephemeral Construction)	7	Up-Cycling
6	Raw wood	1	Recycling
6	Manufacturing	2	Recycling
6	Use (Event organizer or Ephemeral Construction)	3	Recycling
6	Discarding	4	Recycling
6	Wood (treated)	5	Recycling
6	Grinding	6	Recycling
6	Panel of particles	7	Recycling
6	Object (OSB/MDF)	8	Recycling
7	Raw wood	1	Energy recovery
7	Manufacturing	2	Energy recovery
7	Use (Event organizer or Ephemeral Construction)	3	Energy recovery
7	Discarding	4	Energy recovery
7	Wood (raw)	5	Energy recovery
7	Grinding	6	Energy recovery
7	Wooden pellets/Compacted Sawdust	7	Energy recovery

7	Hog Fuel	8	Energy recovery
7	Combustion	9	Energy recovery
7	Energy & Flue Gas & Ashes	10	Energy recovery
8	Raw wood	1	Recycling
8	Manufacturing	2	Recycling
8	Use (Event organizer or Ephemeral Construction)	3	Recycling
8	Discarding	4	Recycling
8	Wood (raw)	5	Recycling
8	Grinding	6	Recycling
8	Wooden chips & Sawdust	7	Recycling
8	Stable Floor	8	Recycling
9	Raw wood	1	Recycling
9	Manufacturing	2	Recycling
9	Use (Event organizer or Ephemeral Construction)	3	Recycling
9	Discarding	4	Recycling
9	Wood (raw)	5	Recycling
9	Grinding	6	Recycling
9	Wooden chips & Sawdust	7	Recycling
9	Mulching	8	Recycling
10	Raw wood	1	Recycling
10	Manufacturing	2	Recycling
10	Use (Event organizer or Ephemeral Construction)	3	Recycling
10	Discarding	4	Recycling

10	Wood (raw)	5	Recycling
10	Grinding	6	Recycling
10	Wooden chips & Sawdust	7	Recycling
10	Composting	8	Recycling
11	Raw wood	1	Recycling
11	Manufacturing	2	Recycling
11	Use (Event organizer or Ephemeral Construction)	3	Recycling
11	Discarding	4	Recycling
11	Wood (raw)	5	Recycling
11	Grinding	6	Recycling
11	Wooden chips & Sawdust	7	Recycling
11	Litter	8	Recycling
11	Soiled litter	9	Recycling
11	Composting	10	Recycling

The user may encounter problems when writing formulas instead of numbers in the “time_PARIS” column. In case the user changes the name of one column or “add” one column after downloading the spreadsheet into PowerBI, make sure to download it again. When erasing a spreadsheet, make sure PowerBI forgets about it, in going to “tools” and “transform data”. There, the user must make sure that the spreadsheet is correctly removed. Moreover, spreadsheets using the same name might be problematic, please avoid that.

Figure B and C displays the parameters of the two dashboard’s plug-in. Figure B is displaying those of the map, and the figure C those of the filters. The map uses the three first columns of table A, while figure C uses another spreadsheet, visible table B.

Table B: The spreadsheet used for the chicletSlicer plug-in, to create the filter.

Paris Pilot	image-paris
Up-cycling	https://media1.julesjenn.com/wordpress/wp-content/uploads/2020/05/recycling.jpg
Recycling	https://scx2.b-cdn.net/gfx/news/hires/2018/recycling.jpg
Energy recovery	https://www.laposte.fr/medias/sys_master/images/hed/h37/10300357050398.jpg
Not valorised	https://w.ndtvmg.com/sites/3/2018/12/31151903/year-ender-2018-landfill-india-660x330.jpg
Re-use	https://cdn-s-www.dna.fr/images/0071707F-FB0C-4A47-84CD-1211E0E74B73/NW_raw/la-salle-des-ventes-d-emmaus-mundo-vide-pour-cause-de-covid-19-document-remis-1588154134.jpg

Finally, to link the filter and the map, and make them interactive with one another, the panel data connections. Drop the spreadsheets you wish to link and create links between columns.

As a result, you will see them highlighted as follows, see Figure D. Here, the column “Paris Pilot” and “Business opportunities” are linked.

Figure D: Connect your data

Last but not the least, make sure to use a color-blind color's theme, to be as inclusive as possible. The colour palette used is the “ColorBlindSafe-Longer” palette.

Annex 9: Mapping of the Wood Journeys within Paris

Figure 15: Wood journeys, using the filter “up-cycling”

Figure 16: Wood journeys, using the filter “up-cycling” and “recycling”

Annex 11: Mapping of the home textile Journeys within Amsterdam

Figure 21: Home textile's journeys using the "circular economy" and "rare path" filters

Annex 12: Mapping of the Plastic Journeys within Vejle

Figure 22: General Layout of the plastics' states and transformations within the Vejle Pilot

Figure 23: Plastic's journeys using the "PET" filter

Figure 24: Plastic's journeys using the "PE" filter

Annex 13: Mapping of the Urban Energy within Cluj-Napoca

Figure 25: General Layout of the Energy journeys

The different source of Energy within the city

Disclose the different journeys the urban energy can take, from sources to electricity, through the progress toolbar at the bottom and the type of energy sources' filter at the top. Zoom in and out on the diagram using the tools at the bottom left corner.

Select an Energy source

Path Number ● 3 ● 5 ● 6 ● 7 ● 8 ● 9

Figure 26: Energy journeys using the filter “renewable energy”

Annex 14: Milan material journey mapping

Figure 28: Fruits/Vegetable leftovers' journeys using the “Up-cycling” filter

Figure 29: Fruits/Vegetable leftovers' journeys using the “unchanged” filter

Annex 15: Data used in the Mapping of Wood flows within Paris

ID_PARIS	Activity_PARIS	time_PARIS	Business Opportunities
1	Raw wood	1	Not valorised
1	Manufacturing	2	Not valorised
1	Use (Event organizer or Ephemeral Construction)	3	Not valorised
1	Discarding	4	Not valorised
1	Air, water and earth pollutants	5	Not valorised
3	Raw wood	1	Re-Use
3	Manufacturing	2	Re-Use
3	Use (Event organizer or Ephemeral Construction)	3	Re-Use
3	Storage	4	Re-Use
3	Second-hand	5	Re-Use
3	Use (Event organizer or Ephemeral Construction)	6	Re-Use
4	Raw wood	1	Up-Cycling
4	Manufacturing	2	Up-Cycling
4	Use (Event organizer or Ephemeral Construction)	3	Up-Cycling
4	Storage	4	Up-Cycling
4	Refurbishing	5	Up-Cycling
4	Use (Event organizer or Ephemeral Construction)	6	Up-Cycling
5	Raw wood	1	Up-Cycling
5	Manufacturing	2	Up-Cycling
5	Use (Event organizer or Ephemeral Construction)	3	Up-Cycling
5	Storage	4	Up-Cycling
5	Refurbishing	5	Up-Cycling
5	Re-Manufacturing	6	Up-Cycling
5	Use (Event organizer or Ephemeral Construction)	7	Up-Cycling
6	Raw wood	1	Recycling
6	Manufacturing	2	Recycling
6	Use (Event organizer or Ephemeral Construction)	3	Recycling
6	Discarding	4	Recycling
6	Wood (treated)	5	Recycling
6	Grinding	6	Recycling
6	Panel of particles	7	Recycling
6	Object (OSB/MDF)	8	Recycling
7	Raw wood	1	Energy recovery
7	Manufacturing	2	Energy recovery

7	Use (Event organizer or Ephemeral Construction)	3	Energy recovery
7	Discarding	4	Energy recovery
7	Wood (raw)	5	Energy recovery
7	Grinding	6	Energy recovery
7	Wooden pellets/Compacted Sawdust	7	Energy recovery
7	Hog Fuel	8	Energy recovery
7	Combustion	9	Energy recovery
7	Energy & Flue Gas & Ashes	10	Energy recovery
8	Raw wood	1	Recycling
8	Manufacturing	2	Recycling
8	Use (Event organizer or Ephemeral Construction)	3	Recycling
8	Discarding	4	Recycling
8	Wood (raw)	5	Recycling
8	Grinding	6	Recycling
8	Wooden chips & Sawdust	7	Recycling
8	Stable Floor	8	Recycling
9	Raw wood	1	Recycling
9	Manufacturing	2	Recycling
9	Use (Event organizer or Ephemeral Construction)	3	Recycling
9	Discarding	4	Recycling
9	Wood (raw)	5	Recycling
9	Grinding	6	Recycling
9	Wooden chips & Sawdust	7	Recycling
9	Mulching	8	Recycling
10	Raw wood	1	Recycling
10	Manufacturing	2	Recycling
10	Use (Event organizer or Ephemeral Construction)	3	Recycling
10	Discarding	4	Recycling
10	Wood (raw)	5	Recycling
10	Grinding	6	Recycling
10	Wooden chips & Sawdust	7	Recycling
10	Composting	8	Recycling
11	Raw wood	1	Recycling
11	Manufacturing	2	Recycling
11	Use (Event organizer or Ephemeral Construction)	3	Recycling
11	Discarding	4	Recycling
11	Wood (raw)	5	Recycling
11	Grinding	6	Recycling
11	Wooden chips & Sawdust	7	Recycling
11	Litter	8	Recycling

11	Soiled litter	9	Recycling
11	Composting	10	Recycling

Annex 16: Data used in the Mapping of food waste flows within Milan

ID_MILAN	Activity_MILAN	time_MILAN	OUTPUTS nature
1	Farming	1	Not valorised
1	Vegetables/fruits	2	Not valorised
1	General Food Market	2	Not valorised
1	Food Market	3	Not valorised
1	Leftovers	4	Not valorised
1	Discarding to landfills	5	Not valorised
1	Methane	6	Not valorised
2	Farming	1	Unchanged
2	Vegetables/fruits	2	Unchanged
2	General Food Market	2	Unchanged
2	Food Market	3	Unchanged
2	Leftovers	4	Unchanged
2	Dumpster Diving	5	Unchanged
3	Farming	1	Unchanged
3	Vegetables/fruits	2	Unchanged
3	General Food Market	2	Unchanged
3	Food Market	3	Unchanged
3	Sold	4	Unchanged
4	Farming	1	Recycling
4	Vegetables/fruits	2	Recycling
4	General Food Market	2	Recycling
4	Food Market	3	Recycling
4	Leftovers	4	Recycling
4	Composting	5	Recycling
4	Compost	6	Recycling
5	Farming	1	Energy Recovery
5	Vegetables/fruits	2	Energy Recovery
5	General Food Market	2	Energy Recovery
5	Food Market	3	Energy Recovery
5	Leftovers	4	Energy Recovery
5	Composting	5	Energy Recovery
5	Biogas	6	Energy Recovery
5	Combustion	7	Energy Recovery
5	Energy	8	Energy Recovery

6	Farming	1	Unchanged
6	Vegetables/fruits	2	Unchanged
6	General Food Market	2	Unchanged
6	Food Market	3	Unchanged
6	Leftovers	4	Unchanged
6	Donnation	5	Unchanged
7	Farming	1	Unchanged
7	Ugly vegetables/fruits	2	Unchanged
7	General Food Market	2	Unchanged
7	Food Market	3	Unchanged
7	Leftovers	4	Unchanged
7	Donnation	5	Unchanged
9	Farming	1	Energy Recovery
9	Vegetables/fruits	2	Energy Recovery
9	General Food Market	2	Energy Recovery
9	Food Market	3	Energy Recovery
9	Leftovers	4	Energy Recovery
9	Sorting	5	Energy Recovery
9	Coffee leftovers	6	Energy Recovery
9	Combustion	7	Energy Recovery
9	Energy	8	Energy Recovery
10	Farming	1	Up-Cycling
10	Vegetables/fruits	2	Up-Cycling
10	General Food Market	2	Up-Cycling
10	Food Market	3	Up-Cycling
10	Leftovers	4	Up-Cycling
10	Sorting	5	Up-Cycling
10	fruit's leftovers	6	Up-Cycling
10	leather-like material	7	Up-Cycling
11	Farming	1	Up-Cycling
11	Vegetables/fruits	2	Up-Cycling
11	General Food Market	2	Up-Cycling
11	Food Market	3	Up-Cycling
11	Leftovers	4	Up-Cycling
11	Sorting	5	Up-Cycling
11	bio-Manufacturing	6	Up-Cycling
12	Farming	1	Up-Cycling
12	Vegetables/fruits	2	Up-Cycling

12	General Food Market	2	Up-Cycling
12	Food Market	3	Up-Cycling
12	Leftovers	4	Up-Cycling
12	Sorting	5	Up-Cycling
12	Beer	6	Up-Cycling
13	Farming	1	Up-Cycling
13	Vegetables/fruits	2	Up-Cycling
13	General Food Market	2	Up-Cycling
13	Food Market	3	Up-Cycling
13	Leftovers	4	Up-Cycling
13	Sorting	5	Up-Cycling
13	Bioplastic	6	Up-Cycling
14	Farming	1	Up-Cycling
14	Vegetables/fruits	2	Up-Cycling
14	General Food Market	2	Up-Cycling
14	Food Market	3	Up-Cycling
14	Leftovers	4	Up-Cycling
14	Sorting	5	Up-Cycling
14	Fabrics	6	Up-Cycling

Annex 17: Data used in the Mapping of wastewater flows within Berlin

ID_BER	Activity_BER	time_BER
1	Residential buildings, offices or industries	1
1	hot/warm wastewater	2
1	Sewer system	3
1	Wastewater pumping station	4
1	Wastewater pressure pipe	5
1	Wastewater Treatment plant	6
1	Cleaned water sent to the river	7
2	Residential buildings, offices or industries	1
2	Residential buildings, offices or industries	2
2	hot/warm wastewater	3
2	Sewer system	4
2	Heat exchanger	5
2	Heat recovery	6
2	Residential buildings, offices or industries	7
3	Residential buildings, offices or industries	1
3	hot/warm wastewater	2
3	Sewer system	3
3	Wastewater pumping station	4
3	Wastewater pressure pipe	5
3	Heat exchanger	6
3	Heat recovery	7
3	Residential buildings, offices or industries	8
4	Residential buildings, offices or industries	1
4	hot/warm wastewater	2
4	Sewer system	3
4	Wastewater pumping station	4
4	Wastewater pressure pipe	5
4	Wastewater Treatment plant	6
4	Heat exchanger	7
4	Heat recovery	8
4	Residential buildings, offices or industries	9

Annex 18: Data used in the Mapping of energy flows within Cluj-Napoca

ID_CLUJ	Activity_CLUJ	time_CLUJ	resources' type
1	Nuclear Energy	1	Nuclear Energy
1	Heat & Radioactive waste & Water vapour	2	Nuclear Energy
1	Mechanical Energy	3	Nuclear Energy
1	Electricity	4	Nuclear Energy
3	Fossil Energy	1	Fossil Energy
3	Coal-fired power plant	2	Fossil Energy
3	Combustion	3	Fossil Energy
3	Heat & Flue gas & Ashes	4	Fossil Energy
3	Mechanical Energy	5	Fossil Energy
3	Electricity	6	Fossil Energy
8	Fossil Energy	1	Fossil Energy
8	Fuel Energy	2	Fossil Energy
8	Combustion	3	Fossil Energy
8	Heat & Flue gas & Ashes	4	Fossil Energy
8	Mechanical Energy	5	Fossil Energy
8	Electricity	6	Fossil Energy
11	Renewable Energy	1	Renewable Energy
11	Wind's Mechanical Energy	2	Renewable Energy
11	Wind turbine	3	Renewable Energy
11	Electricity	4	Renewable Energy
12	Renewable Energy	1	Renewable Energy
12	Rivers	2	Renewable Energy
12	Dams	3	Renewable Energy
12	Hydraulics' Mechanical Energy	4	Renewable Energy
12	Hydraulics' turbine	5	Renewable Energy
12	Electricity	6	Renewable Energy
7	Renewable Energy	1	Renewable Energy
7	Rivers	2	Renewable Energy
7	Hydraulics' Mechanical Energy	3	Renewable Energy
7	Micro/Pico hydro power plant	4	Renewable Energy
7	Electricity	5	Renewable Energy
13	Renewable Energy	1	Renewable Energy
13	Solar Energy	2	Renewable Energy
13	Photovoltaic panels	3	Renewable Energy
13	Electricity	4	Renewable Energy
14	Renewable Energy	1	Renewable Energy
14	Biomass	2	Renewable Energy
14	Combustion	3	Renewable Energy
14	Heat & Flue gas & Ashes	4	Renewable Energy

14	Mechanical Energy	5	Renewable Energy
14	Electricity	6	Renewable Energy
15	Renewable Energy	1	Renewable Energy
15	Biomass	2	Renewable Energy
15	Fermentation	3	Renewable Energy
15	Bio gas	4	Renewable Energy
15	Combustion	5	Renewable Energy
15	Heat & Flue gas	6	Renewable Energy
15	Mechanical Energy	7	Renewable Energy
15	Electricity	8	Renewable Energy

Annex 19: Data used in the Mapping of textile flows within Amsterdam

ID_AMS_B	Activity_AMS_B	time_AMS_B	type of process	type of path in Denmark
1	Product manufacturing	1	Linear	Rare
1	Usage, laundry, maintenance	2	Linear	Rare
1	Discard	3	Linear	Rare
1	Decomposition in the landfills	4	Linear	Rare
1	Earth and Water pollution	5	Linear	Rare
2	Product manufacturing	1	Linear	Traditional
2	Usage, laundry, maintenance	2	Linear	Traditional
2	Discard	3	Linear	Traditional
2	Incineration	4	Linear	Traditional
2	Energy & Flue Gas & Ashes	5	Linear	Traditional
3	Product manufacturing	1		Common
3	Usage, laundry, maintenance	2		Common
3	Discard	3		Common
3	Textile Collection & Sorting	4	Re-use	Common
3	Wearable	5	Re-use	Common
3	2nd-hand clothing	6	Re-use	Common
3	High Quality	7	Re-use	Common
3	Usage, laundry, maintenance	8	Re-use	Common
4	Product manufacturing	1		Common
4	Usage, laundry, maintenance	2		Common
4	Discard	3		Common
4	Textile Collection & Sorting	4	Re-use	Common
4	Wearable	7	Re-use	Common
4	2nd-hand clothing	8	Re-use	Common
4	Sent to Eastern Europe and Africa	9	Re-use	Common
5	Product manufacturing	1		Rare
5	Usage, laundry, maintenance	2		Rare
5	Discard	3		Rare
5	Textile Collection & Sorting	4	Circular	Rare
5	Non wearable	5	Circular	Rare
5	Sorting (natural, synthetic, blended)	6	Circular	Rare
5	Washing and Sorting (type, fiber, color)	7	Circular	Rare
5	Unravelling (knitted)/Shredding (woven or non-woven)	8	Circular	Rare
5	Chemical recycling	9	Circular	Rare
5	Enzymatic process	10	Circular	Rare

5	Separation of synthetic fiber from natural components	11	Circular	Rare
5	Natural components (liquid)	12	Circular	Rare
5	Bio-based product	13	Circular	Rare
5	Sent to the Industry	14	Circular	Rare
6	Product manufacturing	1		Rare
6	Usage, laundry, maintenance	2		Rare
6	Discard	3		Rare
6	Textile Collection & Sorting	4	Circular	Rare
6	Non wearable	5	Circular	Rare
6	Sorting (natural, synthetic, blended)	6	Circular	Rare
6	Washing and Sorting (type, fiber, color)	7	Circular	Rare
6	Unravelling (knitted)/Shredding (woven or non-woven)	8	Circular	Rare
6	Chemical recycling	9	Circular	Rare
6	Enzymatic process	10	Circular	Rare
6	Separation of synthetic fiber from natural components	11	Circular	Rare
6	Spinning	12	Circular	Rare
6	Synthetic yarn	13	Circular	Rare
6	Textile Finishing	14	Circular	Rare
6	Product manufacturing	15	Circular	Rare
7	Product manufacturing	1		Rare
7	Usage, laundry, maintenance	2		Rare
7	Discard	3		Rare
7	Textile Collection & Sorting	4	Circular	Rare
7	Non wearable	5	Circular	Rare
7	Sorting (natural, synthetic, blended)	6	Circular	Rare
7	Washing and Sorting (type, fiber, color)	7	Circular	Rare
7	Unravelling (knitted)/Shredding (woven or non-woven)	8	Circular	Rare
7	Extrusion (Synthetic fiber)	9	Circular	Rare
7	Polyester pellets	10	Circular	Rare
7	Synthetic yarn	11	Circular	Rare
7	Textile Finishing	12	Circular	Rare
7	Product manufacturing	13	Circular	Rare
8	Product manufacturing	1		Common
8	Usage, laundry, maintenance	2		Common
8	Discard	3		Common
8	Textile Collection & Sorting	4	Circular	Common
8	Non wearable	5	Circular	Common
8	Sorting (natural, synthetic, blended)	6	Circular	Common
8	Washing and Sorting (type, fiber, color)	7	Circular	Common
8	Unravelling (knitted)/Shredding (woven or non-woven)	8	Circular	Common

8	Mechanical recycling	9	Circular	Common
8	Spinning	10	Circular	Common
8	Synthetic/Natural/Blended yarns	11	Circular	Common
8	Textile Finishing	12	Circular	Common
8	Product manufacturing	13	Circular	Common
9	Product manufacturing	1		Common
9	Usage, laundry, maintenance	2		Common
9	Discard	3		Common
9	Textile Collection & Sorting	4	Circular	Common
9	Non wearable	5	Circular	Common
9	Sorting (natural, synthetic, blended)	6	Circular	Common
9	Washing and Sorting (type, fiber, color)	7	Circular	Common
9	Unravelling (knitted)/Shredding (woven or non-woven)	8	Circular	Common
9	Chemical recycling	9	Circular	Common
9	Spinning	10	Circular	Common
9	Synthetic/Natural/Blended yarns	11	Circular	Common
9	Textile Finishing	12	Circular	Common
9	Product manufacturing	13	Circular	Common

Annex 20: Date used in the Mapping of Plastic flows within Vejle

ID_V ejle	Activity_VEJLE	time_ VEJLE	PVC_p aths	PET_pa ths	PP_path s	PE_paths	PS_paths
1	Plastic not/wrongly sorted at home	1		PET (bottles)	PP (lunch box)	PE (shampoo bottle)	PS (yoghurt cup)
1	Common trash	2		PET (bottles)	PP (lunch box)	PE (shampoo bottle)	PS (yoghurt cup)
1	Incineration	3		PET (bottles)	PP (lunch box)	PE (shampoo bottle)	PS (yoghurt cup)
3	Plastic collection from plastic trashbins	1		PET (bottles)	PP (lunch box)	PE (shampoo bottle)	PS (yoghurt cup)
3	Sorting (thermoplastics)	2		PET (bottles)	PP (lunch box)	PE (shampoo bottle)	PS (yoghurt cup)
3	Depolluting & Ferrous material removing	3		PET (bottles)	PP (lunch box)	PE (shampoo bottle)	PS (yoghurt cup)
3	Optical/Density/Buoyancy sorting	4		PET (bottles)	PP (lunch box)	PE (shampoo bottle)	PS (yoghurt cup)
3	Shredding	5		PET (bottles)	PP (lunch box)	PE (shampoo bottle)	PS (yoghurt cup)
3	Flakes of PET, PP, PS, PE	6		PET (bottles)	PP (lunch box)	PE (shampoo bottle)	PS (yoghurt cup)
3	Compressor	7		PET (bottles)	PP (lunch box)	PE (shampoo bottle)	PS (yoghurt cup)
3	Object	8		PET (bottles)	PP (lunch box)	PE (shampoo bottle)	PS (yoghurt cup)
4	Plastic collection from plastic trashbins	1		PET (bottles)	PP (lunch box)	PE (shampoo bottle)	PS (yoghurt cup)
4	Sorting (thermoplastics)	2		PET (bottles)	PP (lunch box)	PE (shampoo bottle)	PS (yoghurt cup)
4	Depolluting & Ferrous material removing	3		PET (bottles)	PP (lunch box)	PE (shampoo bottle)	PS (yoghurt cup)

4	Optical/Density/Buoyancy sorting	4		PET (bottles)	PP (lunch box)	PE (shampoo bottle)	PS (yoghurt cup)
4	Shredding	5		PET (bottles)	PP (lunch box)	PE (shampoo bottle)	PS (yoghurt cup)
4	Flakes of PET, PP, PS, PE	6		PET (bottles)	PP (lunch box)	PE (shampoo bottle)	PS (yoghurt cup)
4	Sheets' compressor	7		PET (bottles)	PP (lunch box)	PE (shampoo bottle)	PS (yoghurt cup)
4	Object	8		PET (bottles)	PP (lunch box)	PE (shampoo bottle)	PS (yoghurt cup)
5	Plastic collection from plastic trashbins	1		PET (bottles)	PP (lunch box)	PE (shampoo bottle)	PS (yoghurt cup)
5	Sorting (thermoplastics)	2		PET (bottles)	PP (lunch box)	PE (shampoo bottle)	PS (yoghurt cup)
5	Depolluting & Ferrous material removing	3		PET (bottles)	PP (lunch box)	PE (shampoo bottle)	PS (yoghurt cup)
5	Optical/Density/Buoyancy sorting	4		PET (bottles)	PP (lunch box)	PE (shampoo bottle)	PS (yoghurt cup)
5	Shredding	5		PET (bottles)	PP (lunch box)	PE (shampoo bottle)	PS (yoghurt cup)
5	Flakes of PET, PP, PS, PE	6		PET (bottles)	PP (lunch box)	PE (shampoo bottle)	PS (yoghurt cup)
5	Heating/Purifying & Extruding	7		PET (bottles)	PP (lunch box)	PE (shampoo bottle)	PS (yoghurt cup)
5	Filament (except PVC)	8		PET (bottles)	PP (lunch box)	PE (shampoo bottle)	PS (yoghurt cup)
5	3D printing	9		PET (bottles)	PP (lunch box)	PE (shampoo bottle)	PS (yoghurt cup)
5	Object	10		PET (bottles)	PP (lunch box)	PE (shampoo bottle)	PS (yoghurt cup)
6	Plastic collection from plastic trashbins	1			PP (lunch box)	PE (shampoo bottle)	

6	Sorting (thermoplastics)	2			PP (lunch box)	PE (shampoo bottle)
6	Depolluting & Ferrous material removing	3			PP (lunch box)	PE (shampoo bottle)
6	Optical/Density/Buoyancy sorting	4			PP (lunch box)	PE (shampoo bottle)
6	Shredding	5			PP (lunch box)	PE (shampoo bottle)
6	Flakes of PET, PP, PS, PE	6			PP (lunch box)	PE (shampoo bottle)
6	Chemical recycling (except PS, PET)	7			PP (lunch box)	PE (shampoo bottle)
6	New polymer	8			PP (lunch box)	PE (shampoo bottle)
7	Plastic collection from plastic trashbins	1		PET (bottles)		
7	Sorting (thermoplastics)	2		PET (bottles)		
7	Depolluting & Ferrous material removing	3		PET (bottles)		
7	Optical/Density/Buoyancy sorting	4		PET (bottles)		
7	Shredding	5		PET (bottles)		
7	Flakes of PET	6		PET (bottles)		
7	Heating/Purifying & Extruding	7		PET (bottles)		
7	Melting into fiber	8		PET (bottles)		
7	Spinning and weaving	9		PET (bottles)		

7	Synthetic fabric	10		PET (bottles)			
8	Plastic collection from plastic trashbins	1		PET (bottles)			
8	Sorting (thermoplastics)	2		PET (bottles)			
8	Depolluting & Ferrous material removing	3		PET (bottles)			
8	Optical/Density/Buoyancy sorting	4		PET (bottles)			
8	Shredding	5		PET (bottles)			
8	Flakes of PET	6		PET (bottles)			
8	Pulverisation	7		PET (bottles)			
8	Fine powder	8		PET (bottles)			
10	Plastic collection from plastic trashbins	1		PET (bottles)	PP (lunch box)	PE (shampoo bottle)	PS (yoghurt cup)
10	Sorting (thermoplastics)	2		PET (bottles)	PP (lunch box)	PE (shampoo bottle)	PS (yoghurt cup)
10	Depolluting & Ferrous material removing	3		PET (bottles)	PP (lunch box)	PE (shampoo bottle)	PS (yoghurt cup)
10	Optical/Density/Buoyancy sorting	4		PET (bottles)	PP (lunch box)	PE (shampoo bottle)	PS (yoghurt cup)
10	Shredding	5		PET (bottles)	PP (lunch box)	PE (shampoo bottle)	PS (yoghurt cup)
10	Flakes of PET, PP, PS, PE	6		PET (bottles)	PP (lunch box)	PE (shampoo bottle)	PS (yoghurt cup)
10	Heating/Purifying & Extruding	7		PET (bottles)	PP (lunch box)	PE (shampoo bottle)	PS (yoghurt cup)

10	High Quality Pellets	8		PET (bottles)	PP (lunch box)	PE (shampoo bottle)	PS (yoghurt cup)
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